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Abbreviations

CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CRIS	Current Research Information System
CRUP	Conselho de Reitores das Universidades Portuguesas (Council of Rectors of Portuguese Universities)
EUR	Euro
FCCN	Fundação para a Computação Científica Nacional (Foundation for National Scientific Computing)
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (Foundation for Science and Technology)
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
IPL	Impact Pathway Logic
IR	Institutional Repository
OA	Open Access
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OJS	Open Journal System
OS	Open Science
PathOS	Open Science Impact Pathways (Horizon Europe Project)
RCAAP	Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal (Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal)
RCOMUM	Repositório Comum (Common Repository)
SaaS	Software as a Service
SARC	Serviço de Alojamento de Revistas Científicas (Scientific Journals Hosting Service)
SARDC	Serviço de Alojamento de Repositório de Dados Científicos (Scientific Data Repositories Hosting Service)
SARI	Serviço de Alojamento de Repositórios Institucionais (Institutional Repositories Hosting Service)
SCEUR	Serviço Centralizado de Estatísticas de Utilização de Repositórios (Centralised Service of Statistics on the Use of Repositories)
SDR	Social Discount Rate

Executive Summary

This document summarises the assessment of RCAAP—the Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal. The evaluation combined a tailored Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to measure short-term, quantifiable impacts with an impact pathway approach to capture RCAAP broader scientific and societal contributions over time.

The CBA focuses on a 20-year period (2006-2026) in order to capture the full lifecycle of RCAAP. On the cost side, the analysis considers the operational and set-up costs borne by RCAAP at the central level, as well as by the different institutions for their repositories. The identified benefits are primarily costs savings due to the pooling of resources allowed by RCAAP. By providing hosting services free of charge to voluntary organisations, RCAAP unlocks labour costs savings (i.e., a single team at the central level can manage several repositories more efficiently than having multiple teams across all the institutions) and data storage costs savings (by sharing servers). RCAAP also probably leads to access costs savings, by making the content of RCAAP more easily searchable and accessible to users, though this was not possible to fully integrate this benefit in the analysis. Overall, the CBA shows a net benefit of EUR 1.1 million for RCAAP over the 2006-2026 period. This implies that the benefits of RCAAP are 32% higher than its costs. This estimate is conservative, meaning that the ratio would probably be better by integrating access costs savings.

Beyond short-term benefits captured by the CBA, RCAAP can support long-term improvements in the academic sector, especially at the national level. At this stage, only a minority (about 40%) of Portuguese scientific publications are available on RCAAP Repositories, but this could improve in the future. Anecdotes from the interviewees suggested that the wider society could benefit from RCAAP in the form of increase knowledge or culture. For instance, patients with specific medical conditions would find relevant content on their diseases on the repositories and even contact the researchers on that basis.

This assessment highlights the complexity of evaluating the impact of Open Science resources like RCAAP. Key lessons include the difficulty to estimate the number of users from web analytics or internal monitoring tools, the challenges to define a credible and robust counterfactual scenario and the difficulties to attribute costs and benefits when the project involves multiple layers of stakeholders. Despite these issues, the analysis confirmed that RCAAP provided some significant benefits to its institutional users (through costs savings). Beyond these core gains, RCAAP has the potential to strengthen the academic ecosystem of Portugal in the longer run, notably if it increases its share of covered publications.

Introduction

The focus of the case study is **RCAAP (Repositórios Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal), i.e., the Portugal Open Access Science Repository**. This Open Science (OS) initiative is designed to enhance the visibility, accessibility, and dissemination of Portuguese research. RCAAP is a network of Institutional Repositories (IR) of several Portuguese institutions aggregated by a single Portal. RCAAP also provides several additional services at the central level to the participant institutions and users. Consequently, RCAAP acts as a single-entry point to Portuguese scientific evidence, including documents and, to a lesser extent, journals and data. It is operated at the central level by the University of Minho and the Foundation for National Scientific Computing (FCCN) – the digital unit of Portugal's national research funding agency (FCT).

The CBA assesses the costs and benefits of RCAAP, compared to a hypothetical situation where the resource would not have developed.

The analysis draws on various data collection and analytical approaches, including:

- Documentary review
- Quantitative data analysis (e.g., traffic, budget...)
- Users' online survey
- Interviews
- Focus group
- Additional data from other work packages of the PathOS project

The methodological approach is described in greater details in annexe 1.

The findings of this report are structured as follows: Section 1 introduces the RCAAP system, including its overarching architecture, users, and content. Section 2 outlines the impact pathways identified in association with RCAAP. Section 3 presents the complete findings from the Cost-Benefit Analysis (including costs and benefits). Section 4 explores potential additional impacts that could be discussed outside the CBA framework. Lastly, Section 5 offers conclusions and highlights the main challenges encountered during the assessment.

1. RCAAP: A single-entry point to Portuguese scientific content

RCAAP (Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal), i.e., the Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal, is the central system to discover, locate, and retrieve scientific content (including hundreds of thousands of publications, theses, conference proceedings, journal articles, and data) hosted in Portuguese Institutional Repositories (IR).

Overall, **RCAAP targets three primary objectives** that have remained stable since its establishment (Donato, 2010). They include (i) increasing the visibility, accessibility, and dissemination of Portuguese research results, (ii) facilitating access to information regarding these outputs; and (iii) integrating Portugal in the range of international initiatives for Open Access (OA).

1.1 The architecture of RCAAP

Launched in 2008, the RCAAP system consists of various interconnected components that have developed over time (for more details on the history, see Section 1.2). The backbones of the system are the network of IR and the Search Portal, which aggregates their content. They are supported by a technical infrastructure (e.g., for the exchange of metadata). Other additional and supporting services are also provided by RCAAP (see the Figure below for an overview of the architecture).

The backbone of the RCAAP system consists of systems and services that aggregate the metadata of different Portuguese repositories (documents, data) and journals¹. These systems are also used to check the quality of this metadata. The **backbone elements of RCAAP**, present since its inception, thus include:

The **RCAAP Portal** (since 2008) is the single-entry point for all the content related to RCAAP. The Portal collects the metadata on all the aggregated repositories daily, allowing users to search the universe of documents and data (Carvalho et al., 2014).

Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) Validator (since 2009): This module uses a standard protocol (OAI-PMH) to ensure metadata quality and interoperability with other systems and (Carvalho, 2013).

As mentioned previously, RCAAP covers different types of scientific content, but the main one is overwhelmingly (about 85-90% according to interviewees) documents. IR host these

¹ RCAAP does not harvest individual files but scans the content of all aggregated repositories to get their metadata. It should be noted that some repositories are hosted by RCAAP (see below).

documents and mainly use different versions of DSpace². RCAAP has a flexible architecture, allowing it to aggregate different types of repositories. These **types of repositories** allow different modalities of involvement of the institutions:

LOCAL - Local Repositories (since 2008): These IR are directly managed by institutions such as universities or institutes. They retain a very high level of control over their repositories, including hosting, version updates, and technical maintenance. RCAAP aggregates the content of these repositories.

- **SARI - Institutional Repository Hosting Service** (since 2008): This repository type is operated through a service provided by RCAAP at the central level. Any Portuguese institution in the Research and Higher Education system can host its repository with its own individualised brand identity. In addition to customising the visual aspects of the repository, each institution can also define and implement the configuration and parameterisation it considers appropriate to its organisational structure and its policies for self-archiving publications and managing the repository. Repositories made available under this scheme rely on the RCAAP infrastructures (hardware, hosting, connectivity, base systems, applications, security, backup service...). Still, their operation and administration remain the member institutions' responsibility. Applications for the SARI service are opened periodically and publicised on the RCAAP's social networks³. RCAAP provides this service free of charge.
- **RCOMUM - Common Repository** (since 2009-2011): This service is similar to SARI and centrally provided by RCAAP. It targets individual institutions, learned societies, or other bodies that are too small or lack resources to operate their dedicated repositories. Instead, they can upload their scientific content to a collection (i.e., a sub-section) of a "common repository" involving many different organisations.

Members of their institutions use repositories to upload scientific content, which is then made available on the internet to the broader public, typically in Open Access (some content may be closed or under embargo for a specific time, such as theses). In addition to its core repositories, RCAAP also provides **additional hosting services** related to quantitative data hosting (data repositories) and journals hosting, such as:

- **SARDC - Scientific Data Repository Hosting Service** (since 2010): It aims to provide a platform to store and deliver data created and used within the scope of research work of national institutions.
- **SARC - Scientific Journals Hosting Service**⁴ (since 2011): It was created to develop the online publication of scientific journals in Portugal, facilitating the management of

² DSPACE focuses on digital archiving and preservation, with a dedicated administration interface. See <https://dspace.lyrasis.org/>. Several versions of DSpace have been used under RCAAP, with recent updates to DSpace 7/8 ongoing as of October 2024. Specific addons were developed and implemented to complement the classical DSpace service, e.g., to track statistics.

³ As of 2024, there was a short queue for institutions to be able to join SARI.

⁴ The portal for journals hosted on the service is available at: <http://revistas.rcaap.pt>

scientific journals and supporting best practices. The service is based on the Open Journal System (OJS) publishing and management platform. This service is provided under the RCAAP project as a Software as a Service (SaaS), and all the updating, monitoring, backup, and security activities are carried out. In addition to the technical aspects, the service also provides a support service for the journal editor and the training needed to use the system.

Lastly, RCAAP also includes **horizontal services favouring the good functioning of the repositories**, such as statistics and support:

- **SCEUR - Centralised Service of Statistics on the Use of Repositories** (since 2011, now discontinued): It was created to centralise and consolidate usage statistics from the different sources aggregated by RCAAP (Silva, Ramalho, and Ferreira, 2011). This service is not accessible anymore as of 2024.
- **Helpdesk Service** (since 2008): It is accessible via email and telephone. It mainly targets repository managers to ensure the adequate maintenance of their repositories and the resolution of technical issues. It also allows the standardisation of practices between the participating institutions.
- **Training services** (since 2008): They are designed to help users learn how to utilise RCAAP services. This includes training opportunities organised centrally by RCAAP⁵, primarily targeting administrative staff and repository managers of institutions. However, some of the training provided by RCAAP is also relevant for other users, such as academics willing to upload content on their repositories. Additionally, institutions involved in RCAAP can also organise specific training sessions (under various modalities) for their own academic communities. These sessions may cover topics like using the repositories (for searching, downloading, and uploading content) and understanding the organisation's Open Science policy.

⁵ For example, online at <https://elearning.rcaap.pt/>

Figure 1. RCAAP Overall Architecture

Source: Authors

As implied by its architecture, different stakeholders are involved in managing the RCAAP system. It includes (Donato, 2010; Carvalho et al., 2014):

- **National Foundation for Scientific Computation (FCCN / FCT):** It is a private non-profit association of public utility tasked with various operations regarding the network of national research and education in Portugal. It manages the overall coordination and the infrastructures of RCAAP.
- **University of Minho:** It is a Portuguese university and a forerunner of online scientific repositories in the country. It ensures the scientific and technical coordination of RCAAP.
- **Individual institutions (e.g., universities, polytechnical institutes, hospitals, etc.):** They are responsible for the customisation, management, and use of their respective repositories (e.g., definition of the content of the repository, definition of upload policies, etc.). They can choose the type of repository they want to operate (LOCAL, SARI, RCOMUM). The RCAAP Portal aggregates all of them, but they entail different levels of commitment (resources, technical expertise...) and customisation possibilities. Larger institutions tend to opt for LOCAL repositories, while smaller ones often benefit from the shared hosting service provided by RCAAP (SARI or RCOMUM).

Over time, both the number of repositories and the content they contain have grown substantially, with a solid expansion phase in the 2010s. The number of repositories then stabilised in the 2020s. By 2024, a total of 52 individual repositories were thus active and aggregated by RCAAP, encompassing 27 SARI, 24 LOCAL, and 1 RCOMUM.

Figure 2. Number of repositories aggregated by RCAAP by type (2003-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. **Note:** The Figure shows the number of active repositories aggregated by the RCAAP Portal. RCAAP was created in 2008 (see vertical line). Repositories appearing before 2008 correspond to repositories that existed before RCAAP and then were aggregated by the system (e.g., the repository of the University of Minho). Since the RCOMUM covers multiple institutions (they have their own “collections” within this common

repository), the number of aggregated repositories does not directly correspond to the number of organisations RCAAP covers. Work on the RCOMUM started in 2009 but the first collections appeared only in 2011.

As the RCOMUM repository serves several institutions, the number of beneficiary organisations is greater than the number of repositories. By 2024, 121 organisations enjoyed a presence on RCAAP **Figure 3** below shows the evolution of the number of individual institutions benefiting from a repository aggregated by RCAAP (including those sharing the RCOMUM repository).

Figure 3. Number of institutions covered by repositories aggregated by RCAAP by type (2003-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. **Note:** The Figure shows the number of institutions benefiting from active repositories aggregated by the RCAAP Portal. RCAAP was created in 2008 (see vertical line). Institutions appearing before 2008 correspond to those with repositories that existed before RCAAP and then became aggregated by the system (e.g., University of Minho). RCOMUM institutions share the same repository.

Accordingly, the number of documents available on the repositories and through the RCAAP portal grew steadily since the creation of the system and significantly in recent years. Between 2017 and 2023, this number more than doubled, reaching **about 830,000 documents**⁶. Key documents include master’s and PhD theses, scientific articles, and other types of scientific documents⁷. The most common languages are English and Portuguese. LOCAL repositories concentrate the majority of the documents.

⁶ This figure excludes the content hosted by the scientific journal hosting services (SARC), which can be estimated at about 10-15% of the total volume of documents aggregated by the Portal.

⁷ The breakdown by type of documents is not readily available at the level of the entire RCAAP system (i.e., all repositories combined).

Figure 4. Number of documents aggregated by the RCAAP Portal by type of repository (2008-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. Estimated data for 2008 and 2009 based on a linear decay hypothesis. **Note:** The total number of documents aggregated by the RCAAP portal is shown, broken down by type of repositories. The numbers are estimates derived from the observed breakdown between the types of repositories in recent years and correction for the presence of journal articles (10-15% of the total).

RCAAP is not the only aggregator of IR in the world. It uses technologies and protocols (e.g., DSpace, OAI-PMH) that are standard among other repositories (see, e.g., Shearer et al., 2023). What distinguishes RCAAP and makes it a unique resource include the following aspects:

- **Aggregation of Portuguese scientific content:** RCAAP effectively aggregates the content of several IR from Portuguese institutions while allowing a dose of flexibility regarding their operation (e.g., SARI, RCOMUM, or LOCAL repositories). The academic community actively contributes to the system by uploading content to their own repositories. It facilitates discovering and downloading content that would be more fragmented or even hidden otherwise. It is particularly relevant for Portuguese-language documentation. Other aggregators exist, including in the EU, but RCAAP focuses explicitly on this language/geographical area.
- **Pooling of costs and expertise.** By providing several services at the central level (including hosting IR – free of charge for institutions), the RCAAP system allows the pooling of costs and technical expertise, ensuring efficiency gains. It enables institutions to have their own repositories (or a collection of RCOMUM) in ways that would not have been possible otherwise. It is particularly critical in the context of high costs researchers bear, including in Open Access initiatives (e.g., for journals: Klebel and Ross-Hellauer, 2023).

1.2 Development of RCAAP

RCAAP was launched by the University of Minho and FCCN in 2008, capitalising on early initiatives in Portugal and preparatory works in 2006-2008. RCAAP then developed in different steps, spurred by the support of academic institutions, legal developments, and continuous improvements of services (see Figure below for a detailed overview).

Figure 5. Main milestones of the RCAAP project

Source: Authors

Early initiatives promoting Open Access and universities' self-archiving scientific content began taking shape in Portugal in the early 2000s. Notably, the University of Minho led the way with the launch of its IR, RepositoriUM, in 2002-2003 (Rodrigues, Swan, and Baptista, 2013). In 2006, the Council of Rectors of Portuguese Universities (CRUP) formally supported Open Access principles by subscribing to the Berlin Declaration on the Open Access to Knowledge. It enshrined a commitment to Open Access among the relevant academic stakeholders in the country. More specifically, the CRUP paved the way for the development of RCAAP by highlighting the following points:

- It recommended that all Portuguese universities establish IR and defined institutional policies requiring the deposit of their members' publications in these repositories.
- It expressed its support for the interconnection and interoperability between the IR of Portuguese universities by creating a single portal for access to national scientific literature.

In early 2007, CRUP formed a working group dedicated to Open Access, tasked with launching a project that would promote the establishment of more repositories and the development of a national meta-repository. During the mid-2000s, other institutions beyond the University of Minho also began setting up their own repositories, such as ISCTE-IUL, the University of Coimbra, and the University of Porto, with their repositories emerging between 2006 and 2008. However, despite these efforts, the initial development of repositories in Portugal was still concentrated mainly within a small number of institutions and lacked coordinated efforts.

RCAAP was structured and launched rapidly in 2008, following initial investments in 2006-2008. It took approximately 6 to 8 months to develop the core of RCAAP, with contributions from the University of Minho (the technical partner and scientific coordinator) and the National Foundation for Scientific Computation (for infrastructural and information technology aspects). During this phase, the necessary infrastructure and services were established to support the two primary electronic services planned for the project:

- **SARI** aims to allow all Portuguese institutions to open their own repositories without having to maintain technical expertise or bear the related costs.
- **Meta-repository or RCAAP Portal** allows a search of content across all the aggregated repositories (including those hosted by SARI but also by pre-existing institutions).

During the 3rd Open Access Conference held in December 2008, the RCAAP project was publicly launched. Several factors facilitated the rapid emergence and subsequent development of RCAAP. First, the existence of early repositories, particularly that of the University of Minho, provided valuable experience for the development of RCAAP. Second, a consensus among key Portuguese stakeholders regarding Open Science and the use of repositories began to take shape in the mid-2000s.

In the period 2009-2011, several new services were launched by RCAAP to complement the base offer, including quality control (OAI-PMH validator), hosting services (RCOMUM, SARDC, SARC) and horizontal services (SCEUR).

A series of legislative and policy changes at both the national and institutional levels also backed the development of the RCAAP system. Indeed, in 2013, a legal mandate for the deposit of PhD theses on RCAAP repositories was established⁸. It was followed by a similar 2015 law on research benefiting from FCT funding⁹. In parallel, several institutions also introduced formal or informal OS policies and guidelines for their repositories, including incentives for researchers to deposit their documents (e.g., in career evaluations).

From the mid-2010s, the RCAAP system mostly entered into an exploitation and maintenance phase, with the central team concentrating on upgrading the repositories and

⁸ Decreto-Lei n. 115/2023 de 07/08 [Decree-Law no. 115/2023]

⁹ Portaria n. 285/2015 de 15/09 [Ordinance no. 285/2015]

Portal (e.g., shifts to new versions of DSpace) and resolving technical issues. New functionalities were less common, though a significant uphaul of the RCAAP portal is planned for 2025.

1.3 Using RCAAP: how, who, and for what

RCAAP content is accessible through a web browser, either through the RCAAP Portal or directly through the individual repositories. Content is freely downloadable¹⁰ without user registration and typically under Open Access modalities. However, some documents may be under more restrictive access. In particular, the theses (e.g., PhD) or journals articles can face standardised embargo periods of 12 months typically, and up to 36 months in some cases (FCT, 2014; FCT, 2025). After this period, the files become available to RCAAP users. Individual organisations participating in the RCAAP system can define their own OS policies, typically including guidelines on what to upload, under which conditions, and by whom. The documents generally are recorded as PDF files, as shown in the Figure below.

Figure 6. Example of a document made available on the RepositoriUM (aggregated by RCAAP)

Citação: Baptista, S. L., Soares, P. O., Romani, A., Alonso, J. L., & Domingues, L. (2024, December). Engineering arabinose-to-arabitol conversion in industrial *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for sugar beet pulp valorization. *Industrial Crops and Products*. Elsevier BV. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2024.119718>

Resumo(s): Arabitol, a promising low-calorie sweetener for the food industry, faces production challenges due to the high costs and the environmental impact of conventional chemical methods, as well as the inefficiency of biological approaches using native arabitol-producing yeasts. The *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* GRE3 gene encodes an NADPH-dependent aldose reductase, capable of converting various aldoses to their respective sugar alcohols. By leveraging the enzymes broad substrate specificity, the simultaneous conversion of xylose and arabinose into xylitol and arabitol, respectively, was achieved. This study showcases the feasibility of using engineered industrial yeast strains, overexpressing the native GRE3 gene, for the one-step conversion of arabinose to arabitol. Engineered strains (PE22-pGRE3, PE22-pGRE3-XII5, CA11-pGRE3, CA11-pGRE3-XII5, CAT1-pGRE3 and CAT1-pGRE3-XII5) exhibited successful arabinose-to-arabitol conversion, with a 3.5-fold variation in arabitol concentrations across strains. Further enhancement of the best-performing strain through overexpression of the GAL2 gene significantly improved arabinose transport, resulting in a 1.95-fold increase in arabitol productivity. This engineered strain, free of heterologous genes, also demonstrated its potential by converting arabinose-rich sugar-beet pulp hydrolysate into arabitol, reaching a titer of 15g/L with a yield of 1g/g. This study represents the first example of arabitol production from agro-food waste using genome-edited *S. cerevisiae* strains, which contain no foreign genes, as a versatile and efficient host.

Tipo: Artigo

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Arbitragem científica: yes

Acesso: Acesso aberto

Aparece nas coleções: CEB - Publicações em Revistas/Séries Internacionais / Publications in International Journals/Series

Ficheiros deste registo:

Ficheiro	Descrição	Tamanho	Formato
document_58007_1.pdf		15,11 MB	Adobe PDF

[Ver/Abriu](#)

Source: Authors (extracted on 18/10/2024: <https://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/handle/1822/93224>)

¹⁰ Some documents may not be downloadable right away, for instance if they are under temporary embargo. In these cases, the files become available once the embargo period is over.

Primary data collection for this case study allowed a refinement of our understanding of RCAAP uses. It notably included a survey to users¹¹.

As mentioned above, the RCAAP system enables users to search and download content without requiring account creation or registration. **As a result, there is no detailed user profiling or collection of extensive personal information aside from anonymously gathered statistics.** The data collected includes Google Analytics indicators and internal metrics developed by RCAAP (particularly regarding document download counts). This information has been further supplemented by insights obtained through the users' survey.

Salient facts regarding RCAAP users emerge from the different sources, especially from the aforementioned survey. Firstly, most RCAAP users belong to the academic community (researchers or other administrative/support staff, such as librarians). Secondly, the use of RCAAP and its component IR is strongly concentrated in Portugal and Portuguese-speaking countries, which aligns with expectations. Thirdly, the RCAAP system has different types of uses, with a differential involvement of different populations.

As revealed by the above-mentioned users' survey, more than 90% of RCAAP users work or study in higher education institutions/universities (88%) or research centres (3%). Other organisations, especially those in the private sector, were much more marginal (see **Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Organisations of work/study of RCAAP respondents

¹¹ The survey sample was not based on a probability sampling methodology. By comparing the survey results to data on visits, it was noted that Portugal is somewhat overrepresented. However, we were not only interested in visitors to the RCAAP Portal and Institutional Repositories, but also by internal users (e.g., librarians and researchers feeding the system by uploading content). This population is almost exclusively Portugal-based on strongly engaged with the system. There were no other sources on evidence available to describe RCAAP users at the time of the case study. We thus considered that the sample distribution was sufficiently robust to provide a meaningful description of the actual uses of RCAAP. On this basis, it is also deemed suitable for application in the cost-benefit analysis. Further details are provided in the Annex 1.

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 190 respondents who actively use RCAAP.

Respondents thus mostly held research roles (47%), but a substantial proportion held administrative roles (e.g., librarians, at 25%). Other significant functions included students (11%, excluding PhD students, who accounted for 24% of the total – as part of the research roles). This implies that many users of the service are students performing research at an early stage. Other notable users had management (9%) or technical (e.g., lab technicians, information technology specialists, 5%) roles.

Figure 8. Main functions of RCAAP respondents

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 190 respondents with an active use of RCAAP. Admin = Administrative, Mgt. = Management, Tech. = Technical.

When zooming in on the respondents with research roles, we indeed observed a strong prominence of young PhD researchers (52% of this sub-group), while the remaining half is quite balanced in terms of seniority.

Figure 9. Academic positions of respondents with a research role

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 86 respondents with a research role and an active use of RCAAP.

RCAAP users can perform different actions depending on their positions and interests.

The main use of RCAAP concerns searching and downloading scientific content via the Portal or the repositories. Some users (almost exclusively Portuguese researchers and librarians¹²) can also deposit scientific content in their repositories, fuelling the RCAAP system. Other more horizontal or occasional uses include training/support measures and benefits linked to the internal life of institutions (e.g., career evaluation internal reporting using RCAAP statistics...). The interviews with repository managers confirmed the existence of these internal uses. Still, their extent/relevance depended strongly on the actual commitment to perform deposits and remained occasional (e.g., yearly reports...).

The RCAAP survey provides some insights regarding the extent of these usages. As expected, using RCAAP to search and download content is the dominant activity, with 95% of them doing so. Uploading content was less common (45%), which can also be explained by the fact that it can only be performed by academic users with a scientific production or with deposit responsibility. Other activities linked to RCAAP are far less common.

¹² A Brazilian repository (OasisBR) is also aggregated by the RCAAP Portal, and is thus fed by Brazil-based workers.

Figure 10. Activities performed by RCAAP users

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the activities linked to RCAAP performed by the respondents. The sample is composed of 190 respondents who actively use RCAAP. Multiple answers were possible so that the total could be above 100%.

SEARCH AND DOWNLOAD FROM RCAAP

The primary use of the RCAAP system is thus to search and download scientific content from the aggregated IR. Consequently, the primary users hail from the academic community, especially from Portuguese-speaking countries, but also from a worldwide audience and non-academic users.

Estimating the exact volume of users searching and downloading content thanks to RCAAP is challenging due to multiple factors, including the central RCAAP team's loss of access to Google Analytics and the fragmentation of statistics between the different repositories¹³. However, in recent years, the number of unique users accessing the central RCAAP portal to search and download documents can be estimated at about 160,000 on a yearly basis (average for 2017-2024), with a peak in 2020, likely from a COVID effect (see Figure below).

¹³ In particular, the LOCAL repositories do not always provide their use statistics.

Figure 11. Number of unique RCAAP Portal users (2008-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP Google Analytics data. **Note:** Values for 2008-2010 and 2023-2024 were estimated using data on downloads as a proxy. Most users access resources stored in RCAAP IR through other means than the portal, so these figures shall be considered as a lower-bound conservative estimate.

As users can also access content directly through the IR (or via Google Scholar, Google, or other referral sources), **this Figure should be considered as a lower bound.** There are no overarching statistics, but interviews with repository managers and data from the Sapiientia Repository (Google Analytics) suggest that a substantial majority of users arrive at the content through other means. The RCAAP team typically computes the **upper bound of potential users** of the system by aggregating the different members of the Portuguese scientific and academic communities (i.e., students, higher education teachers and researchers), leading to an estimate **of about 531,000 potential users**¹⁴. Even if this figure does not include foreign users, it is likely inflated. It implies that the **number of yearly users likely fall in the 160,000 – 531,000 range.**

Beyond the uncertainties regarding the number of users, it is still possible to monitor activity quite closely. Indeed, the number of downloads by year is well captured by the existing data, with an **estimated 31.8 million downloads per year** (2017-2023 average)¹⁵.

Users that search and download content on the RCAAP Portal primarily stem from Portugal and Portuguese-speaking countries. Indeed, according to the RCAAP survey, 96%

¹⁴ Based on <https://www.pordata.pt/pt/>

¹⁵ Estimate based on data for 39 repositories, extrapolated to the total number of repositories using data on the distribution of documents by repository.

of users using RCAAP to download content hailed from Portugal, 1.7% from Brazil, 0.6% from Angola/Cabo Verde (each), and 1.1% from Spain. This mirrors the situation for the entire sample of users (i.e., including users performing only deposits) and is confirmed by other lines of evidence from the interviews, repository-level data, and RCAAP portal data.

Search and download behaviours are pretty heterogeneous among users. Less than half were frequent users, with either daily (13%) or weekly (33%) use. Conversely, some respondents only had a very occasional approach to the system, with 28% using it monthly and 22% even less (quarterly or 1-2 times a year). The data and interviews suggested that administrative staff (e.g., librarians repository managers) frequently used RCAAP for search and download (26% daily use, 36% weekly use). By contrast, researchers had a notable but slightly less frequent use of the system (daily use 10%, weekly use 29%). Moreover, use among academics was driven by PhD students (14% daily use, 30% weekly use) and research fellows/associate professors (14% daily use, 29% weekly use), while more senior staff relied on it less frequently.

Figure 12. Frequency of use of RCAAP for search and download

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 180 respondents who actively use RCAAP for search and download.

RCAAP users collected various types of documents on the IR or the Portal. Among users accessing RCAAP for downloads, theses and dissertations were the primary type of collected content, with 85% of respondents. Scientific articles closely followed it at 81.11%. Other types of content were less commonly downloaded, though it reached significant figures for books (45%) and reports (28.89%). Conference-related items were less popular (15.56%). Other types of content (e.g., videos, etc.) were very marginal (2.22%).

Interviews suggest that the users download content for several of their activities, including feeding their research or study activities (e.g., the realisation of theses or scientific articles). The survey essentially confirms these use cases. Indeed, 64% of users noting a contribution of the downloaded content to their theses/dissertations asserted it as strong. It was 51% for scientific documents. Additionally, ten respondents reported that access to RCAAP for search and download was crucial to their work by providing concrete examples. For instance, one

respondent noted that RCAAP enabled him to collect several materials to prepare his thesis in the field of auditing. Other respondents pointed out that the RCAAP access fed specific research projects, including quantitative (e.g., a survey on music in early childhood education) and qualitative ones.

Figure 13. Contribution of content downloaded on RCAAP for the following outputs

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 180 respondents who actively use RCAAP for search and download. For theses and dissertations, 161 users reported a contribution. It was 159 for scientific documents and 78 for other outputs.

Anecdotal evidence from interviews suggests that users outside academia can use the RCAAP content in their daily activities. For instance, it includes access to information by companies for their economic activities, journalists, or the wider public (e.g., to look for information regarding their medical conditions). However, these other uses appear much less common than academic ones and are very difficult to substantiate.

UPLOAD/DEPOSITS TO RCAAP REPOSITORIES

The second large type of use of RCAAP consists of upload/deposits to its component repositories. Consequently, only individuals involved in Portuguese institutions (e.g., universities, research centres, research hospitals, etc.) can perform this task. All types of documents can be uploaded, including theses, scientific articles, conference documents, etc.

The modalities of upload are very diversified. According to the RCAAP survey, the great majority of respondents uploaded content to their repositories manually (77%), i.e., through the repository interface (typically DSpace). A significant minority (37-38%) imported existing data on documents from other sources, such as CIENCIAVITAE (curriculum service for

Portuguese researchers¹⁶) or ORCID. However, other sources were possible (9% of respondents). It included repositories that were connected to a Current Research Information System (CRIS) or similar information systems. In these cases, users typically did not have to go to the repositories' interface to perform the uploads, but documents were automatically imported from these other systems. It was, for instance, allowed in the case of the University of Porto and its SIGARRA system. It implies different relationships to the RCAAP systems and potential differences in time savings.

Figure 14. Modalities of deposit of content to the repositories aggregated by RCAAP

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the modalities of upload to RCAAP Repositories used by the respondents. The sample is composed of 86 respondents who actively use RCAAP for uploads. Multiple answers were possible so that the total could be above 100%.

On the upload side, both librarians and researchers perform most of the uploads to the repositories. Responsibilities for uploads are set at the level of individual institutions, with different policies ranging from full self-archiving by researchers to complete delegation of deposits to librarians. This diversity of situations is clearly visible among the respondents to the survey performing uploads. Indeed, almost an equal number reported that administrative staff (including librarians) were responsible for uploads (64%) followed by researchers for their own work (59%). Other modalities were less common (e.g., researchers doing uploads for other researchers). Overall, the evidence from interviews points out that a significant share of deposits is performed or checked extensively by the librarians (50-90%). In particular, librarians are always responsible for uploading theses and dissertations and are expected to check the

¹⁶ It should be noted that it is also possible for researchers to upload content from RCAAP repositories towards their CIENCIAVITAE profile. As of December 2024, it accounted for 338,000 records present on CIENCIAVITAE (see <https://www.cienciavitae.pt/cv-em-numeros/?lang=en>). According to FCCN analyses, it implies that RCAAP IR generates time savings on behalf of CIENCIAVITAE users (about 3 minutes per record). However, it is not clear whether these types of imports could be performed or not under the counterfactual, given that IR would still exist without RCAAP.

deposits made by researchers in any case (though actual practices depend on available resources).

Figure 15. Responsibilities for uploads in the organisations of respondents

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the responsibilities for upload in the organisations of the respondents. The sample is composed of 86 respondents who actively use RCAAP for uploads. Multiple answers were possible so that the total could be above 100%.

The frequency of uploading to the RCAAP repositories is highly variable and depends on the individual institution. This activity also tends to be cyclical, for instance, when these are defended or when researchers face career evaluations¹⁷. The survey confirms these trends by identifying two main user groups based on their upload frequency. The first group (47% of respondents) uploads content to the repositories quite regularly, i.e., at least monthly or even weekly/daily. This group has a substantial proportion of non-researchers (e.g., administrators, librarians...), which can be explained by their responsibilities to upload some content on behalf of researchers (at least in some institutions). The second group (53% of respondents) has a much less frequent upload habit, with quarterly or fewer uploads to the repositories. It includes many researchers backed by qualitative evidence from repository managers' interviews. The difficulties in mobilising researchers for deposits to IR are well documented in the literature (Ten Holter, 2020). In some repositories, the interviews indeed revealed an incomplete participation of researchers in the deposits despite existing policies.

¹⁷ In several organisations, researchers are evaluated based on their scientific output available on the RCAAP IR. It thus constitutes an incentive for them to upload their content. It leads to cyclical spikes of activity, with researchers performing uploads slightly before these evaluation periods. According to the survey, 66% of researchers performing uploads reported that they were evaluated on the basis of the content of the repositories.

Figure 16. Frequency of use of RCAAP for upload

Source: Authors' elaboration on user survey data. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample is composed of 86 respondents who actively use RCAAP for uploads.

RCAAP does not collect harmonised data on the number of users performing uploads, but they are far less numerous than the users searching and gathering content. Establishing a meaningful number of users is moreover complexified by the variety of upload modalities and uneven split of responsibilities within organisations (e.g., a librarian can perform deposits on behalf of multiple researchers in one university, leading to one active user, while in another university, they would all be considered as individual users). As of 2024, the stock of users with deposit rights can nevertheless be estimated at 11,285 – though it includes users performing deposits on behalf of others and potential inactive/very infrequent users.

However, this problem can be somewhat circumvented by analysing the overall number of deposits of documents aggregated by RCAAP. Based on the number of aggregated documents (i.e., excluding journals), it can be estimated that an average of about 77,000 documents were uploaded to RCAAP aggregated IR in recent years (2017-2024).

Figure 17. Number of deposits to IR aggregated by RCAAP (2008-2024)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data. **Note:** Excluding deposits to the journals (10% of the total). Deposits are computed as the difference between total aggregated documents between two consecutive years.

OTHER USES OF RCAAP

Other uses of RCAAP are far less common than the two previously mentioned ones. It includes horizontal / support services provided by RCAAP, and also internal use cases of IR information by participating institutions.

The interviews clearly established that training and helpdesk services provided centrally by RCAAP were primarily used by repository managers and librarians to support their use of the IR and less so by end-users such as researchers. At the local level, librarians typically provide some training or information sessions related to the repositories and RCAAP, either formally or informally. This training activity was usually connected to the institution's Open Science policy (e.g., presentation of principles, other resources, and guidelines) and was not exclusively centred on RCAAP/the IR.

The survey and interviews documented other uses within participating institutions. It included using RCAAP-related statistics to monitor the institutional scientific output, generate insights on performance and trends, and draft reports (e.g., to the University Rectorate).

2. Impact Pathway for RCAAP

The RCAAP system aggregating multiple Portuguese repositories and providing additional services generates numerous effects for its users, including on the upload side (academic community, mainly researchers and librarians), the search and download side (academic community and beyond, including the general public and private sector entities), and for the management of participating institutions. These effects are expected to materialise through different channels called pathways. These pathways entail resources allowing activities, which themselves lead to outputs, outcomes, and, at a later stage, fully-fledge impact.

Following the impact pathway logic for Open Science developed in PathOS (Dekker, Karasz, and Stoy, 2023), we provide – in what follows – a description of how funding and resources made available to RCAAP (**inputs**) translate into direct benefits for users (**outputs and outcomes**)¹⁸ and advancements (**impacts**) in science, the economy, and society.

The actual materialisation of the impact pathway of RCAAP also depends on **enabling factors**, especially those linked to legal and Open Science policy trends. Enabling factors are conditions or elements that facilitate the implementation and success of the RCAAP project. These factors support the mechanisms through which the project is expected to achieve its desired outcomes.

The legislative framework can be considered an enabling factor facilitating the operation of the RCAAP project. In Portugal, the legislation indeed mandates depositing some content to repositories aggregated by the system, ensuring a steady flow of content. In particular, both Portuguese Master's and PhD theses must be uploaded since the Decreto-Lei n. 115/2023 de 07/08 [Decree-Law no. 115/2023]¹⁹. It was complemented in 2015 by another legal document (Portaria n.º 285/2015 de 15/09 [Ordinance no. 285/2015]) mandating the deposit of all outputs benefiting from FCT funding.

Similarly, **Open Science policies, guidelines, and incentives also form valuable enabling factors that** foster the system. Indeed, they act at different levels (national and institutional) to promote using RCAAP repositories, especially for deposits. They can refer to OS principles-specific guidelines or provide incentives (negative or positive) for deposits. Examples include

¹⁸ Short- and long-term outcomes specifically related to RCAAP fall within the categories of indicators developed and reported in the PathOS [Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#). For example, in terms of economic impact, the indicator 'cost-savings' includes short-term outcomes—such as time savings—which are also considered in the cost-benefit analysis of RCAAP. Data storage costs savings also fall under this category.

¹⁹ "1 - A digital copy of the doctoral theses (...) and master's dissertations must be deposited in a repository belonging to the Open Access Scientific Open Access Scientific Repository of Portugal, operated by the Foundation for Science and Technology, I. P.

2 - The deposit aims at the treatment and preservation of the referred scientific outputs, as well as the dissemination, in Open Access regime, of the scientific production that is not subject to restrictions or restrictions or embargoes."

the FCT Open Access Policy at the national level (mandating the deposit of FCT-funded research) or the Policy of the University of Minho, which had a financial incentive policy in 2005 for deposits. Other institutions use deposits for career evaluations, contributing to uptake.

Regarding **inputs**, the RCAAP system benefits from **funding** to support the development, maintenance, and operation of its overarching architecture and component repositories. It encapsulates investment costs at the central level and for LOCAL repositories to set up the entire system (e.g., server for the Portal and repositories...). Maintenance funding mainly targets staff costs for technical experts. Other operational costs are mostly staff-related as well, pertaining to the wages of librarians, administrators, managers, and researchers involved in the design, daily running of the repositories/RCAAP, as well as for the deposit of content to the repositories (see Section 3.2 for a detailed discussion of costs). Due to this cost structure, **technical expertise and skills from the involved staff are also critical**. It entails different types of skills, such as technical (especially IT-related), administrative/librarian, and scientific. The scarcest resource in the context of Portugal refers to technical skills, which notably entails benefits to centralisation and pooling via RCAAP. Larger institutions can typically employ some technical specialists as well, especially for LOCAL repositories, where they must act for the daily maintenance at the institutional level. RCAAP employs about 9 FTE at the central level. Individual repositories have teams of various sizes depending on their organisation, but interviews and a previous survey converge to suggest typical teams of about 1-5 FTE (Shearer, Nakano, and Rodrigues, 2023). The **governance of RCAAP**, including an organisation with different layers (i.e., RCAAP Central level, different institutions managing their repositories, etc.) is also central as an input for the project. This governance can indeed support the good maintenance and development of the system.

These inputs then lead to **different activities**, many of which have already been introduced in Section 1.3. They are often interconnected. **The Development and Maintenance of the RCAAP Central System (Portal, Hosting Services, and Support Services)** was the first activity to launch the entire system. It involved the technical work of building, updating, and maintaining the core infrastructure of RCAAP, which includes the central Portal for users and centralised repositories (SARI/RCOMUM, alongside other hosting services for journals and data) where content is stored. Ongoing maintenance and upgrading (e.g., moving to new versions of DSpace) ensure the continuity and improvement of the service. **The Customisation, Operation, and Maintenance of Individual Repositories** are necessary to feed the RCAAP system. Each institution may have specific needs (e.g., organisation of collections, rights of users, statistical monitoring, integration with other systems...), so the individual repositories are tailored accordingly. This involves ongoing operational management, technical support, and periodic updates to ensure they remain functional and secure within the overall RCAAP framework. The institutions' degree of independence/complexity depends on the type of repository they have chosen. LOCAL repositories have the most flexibility but also bear more costs and issues on their own compared to the SARI/RCOMUM options. **Definition and**

Updating of Individual Repository Policies ensure that technical and organisational aspects are well aligned. Policies regarding content curation, data protection, and document submission must be clearly defined for each repository. These policies may evolve over time based on regulatory changes, user feedback, or technological advancements, requiring regular updates. According to interviews, these policies may be formalised (e.g., repository policy as part of a broader OS policy document, specific guidelines) or more informal.

Deposit of Documents on the Repositories (Including Metadata Curation/Checks and Uploads of the Documents) is the core task of making repositories and the RCAAP system populated by actual content. Depending on the institution, this process involves different stakeholders, such as researchers, librarians, or administrative staff. Metadata is curated and checked to ensure that all documents are appropriately categorised and searchable, with varying modalities depending on the institution. **Dissemination and Training Activities** ensure the different users' awareness of the system and its good use. RCAAP performs these activities at the central level (e.g., through its e-learning portal), mainly targeting librarians and repository managers. However, institutions also train and communicate about their repositories to their communities of users, including students and researchers. RCAAP also operates the **Helpdesk**, which targets repository managers and their teams to resolve potential technical issues.

The activities above directly lead to the materialisation of several outputs. Thanks to the development of the RCAAP system and its component repositories, standard repositories (especially using DSpace) are becoming more available. They are backed by the **support of the RCAAP helpdesk** (e.g., helpdesk support tickets being answered), as well as by the **provision of training** by both the RCAAP central team (e.g., e-learning lessons viewed) and the librarians of individual institutions (e.g., awareness raising sessions in their universities). As a result of the development of these repositories and the related deposit of documents by users, **the main output of the system is increased availability, searchability** (through the repositories, the Portal, and other external tools such as Google Scholar), **and visibility of Portuguese research outputs.** Some outputs of the activities are also related to the inner workings of institutions. Indeed, the operation of repositories and the connected horizontal services (especially statistics) link to benefits of this nature. It includes allowing **improved monitoring and tracking of research outputs** (e.g., through statistics) and **facilitating different management issues** (e.g., career evaluation, internal reporting...).

These outputs are fairly easily measurable or assessed qualitatively. **In turn, they translate into outcomes either in the short or longer terms.** Outcomes notably include some of the critical benefits of the RCAAP system, with the direct ones (especially the academic-oriented outcomes) being integrated into the CBA. Other outcomes, corresponding in particular to more indirect or non-core benefits (e.g., cultural benefits), will not be directly covered by the CBA (see Section 3 below for a complete discussion of the scope of the CBA). Evidence suggests that, due to its nature and peculiarity, cultural or economic benefits linked to RCAAP are relatively small

(e.g., anecdotes about the public using RCAAP to retrieve information on their medical conditions) while academic ones rather prevail. Complex interactions exist between these outcomes; only the main ones will be briefly discussed here.

Academic outcomes include reduced **costs by pooling resources for the repositories allowed by RCAAP** (i.e., shared hosting services provided free of charge to institutions, as compared to each institution operating their repositories independently). The system can also help to **secure time savings related to accessing Portuguese research outputs**. The mechanisms for such savings include the availability of resources on the RCAAP portal, i.e., through a single interface. However, interviewees also pointed out that RCAAP allow an aggregation of information through its back-end, that can be exploited by other services (e.g., Google Scholar). As a consequence, access is facilitated even if users do not directly use the Portal. In theory, the RCAAP system may also lead to time savings for uploading/submitted scientific content, but alternatives to RCAAP may use similar systems (or even DSPACE), so these savings are likely small if existent at all. The **increased audience of Portuguese research outputs** will also be a core academic outcome allowed by the Portal and the repositories, leading to increased readings/downloads of content. Lastly, **the system may reduce direct costs for institutions and researchers to access research by making PDFs freely available**. **However**, in Portugal, a strong pooling effort (e.g., through the B-ON service) has already been achieved so the specific gains of RCAAP may only be a marginal improvement. These short-term academic outcomes could potentially lead to **enhanced productivity, for both administrators and researchers**, mainly through the channel of saved time and the pooling of resources.

Besides pure academic benefits, **RCAAP could also promote the development of new research and, with a much lower probability, entrepreneurial ideas by making the materials more visible and accessible**. This could take the form of greater industry-academia collaboration, though the preliminary evidence from Work Package 3 and interviews suggests that these linkages are infrequent, and not necessarily linked to RCAAP. The **internal management of educational institutions** such as universities would also be improved by **securing time gains**. For instance, tracking the universities' scientific output and the facilitation of managerial tasks allowed by RCAAP would indeed lead to time savings, securing economic gains. Lastly, the increased availability and searchability/visibility of Portuguese research outputs could secure **increased learning and awareness opportunities** for both academic and other users. Indeed, this entails a curiosity-driven perspective, as documented by some anecdotes during the interviews (for instance, people with medical conditions can learn more about their diseases by reading materials freely available on the RCAAP repositories. In the longer term, it can lead to **increased knowledge and cultural benefits at the societal level**, though the scope of this benefit is challenging to estimate.

In the long-run, **the long-term outcomes from RCAAP could translate into even broader impacts**. As such, these impacts are more difficult to capture analytically and are outside the

scope of the CBA. Assessing causality is also challenging. For instance, collaborations between industry and academia were detected thanks to the repository content in the case of the University of Minho (Rodrigues et al., 2023). Still, the origins of this collaboration can be difficult to track. It is expected that the core impacts will be academic. In contrast, the others are more speculative/uncertain and likely limited in magnitude (see Section 4. on benefits beyond CBA for further details).

This case study seeks to measure some of RCAAP's impacts by integrating a CBA perspective²⁰ with an impact pathways framework. The CBA was employed to precisely assess the impacts clearly and directly attributable to RCAAP, focusing on the short-term outcomes it generates for its users, such as cost savings due to pooling or facilitated access to research outputs (Section 3). In contrast, the long-term outcomes are explored within a broader causal pathways analysis, recognising that such outcomes are more marginal and often involve multiple influencing factors, and a direct causal link to RCAAP cannot always be established. Specifically, the long-term outcomes of RCAAP are discussed using qualitative and quantitative evidence.

²⁰ The cost-benefit analysis adopts a micro-economical perspective. This means that indirect (i.e. on secondary markets) and wider effects (e.g. induced impacts or effects on other categories of stakeholders, or economies) are often excluded from the analysis. The choice is to avoid that the analysis relies on assumptions whose reliability is difficult to check as well as any risk of double-counting.

Figure 18. RCAAP Impact Pathway

Source: Authors' elaboration based on primary data (interviews, survey...) and desk research

Note: While certain elements of this Impact Pathway Logic (IPL) - such as inputs, activities, and outputs – may be directly controlled by the stakeholders involved in RCAAP (sphere of control), others fall outside its direct control (sphere of influence and sphere of interest). The sphere of influence is an intermediate category regarding the degree of control of stakeholders involved in RCAAP (notably depending on the performance and engagement of potential users). The final stage (impacts) remains beyond both the direct control and influence of RCAAP stakeholders. However, impacts are certainly of high interest to funders, policy makers, and hence, the RCAAP community. The scope of the CBA is highlighted in red to mark a difference between the benefits entirely triggered by using RCAAP and benefits beyond those captured by the CBA, such as the long-term outcomes highlighted in blue.

3. CBA analysis

The cost-benefit analysis (CBA) has been used to assess the **short-term outcomes** – as illustrated in the IPL for RCAAP (Section 2) – generated by exploiting RCAAP, focusing particularly on effects directly attributable to the system on the functioning of the academic sector. These impacts primarily apply to the **higher education and research institutions** involved in RCAAP and their users (e.g., researchers, administrative and technical staff, students, etc.).

The analysis was guided by the CBA framework specifically tailored to the assessment of open science by Delugas et al. (2023). Accordingly, data on costs associated with the setup and operations of RCAAP were collected and compared to the benefits. A net present value²¹ was then estimated.

In terms of scope, the CBA focuses on the **document repositories, the RCAAP Portal, and the core supporting components of the project** (e.g., training by RCAAP). In particular, the data repositories and the journals hosting service are out of scope (see Section 3.1. below).

Data for the CBA analysis was collected thanks to the support of the RCAAP team (University of Minho and FCCN), a review of the relevant literature, and interviews with repository managers. When necessary, specific assumptions were made and justified. The analysis was guided by the CBA framework for open science, as described in Delugas, Catalano, and Vignetti, 2023.

During our analysis of RCAAP, we identified different costs and benefits that could be attributed to its functioning. We provided a comprehensive look at the costs sustained by the different stakeholders involved in the system, including the provider costs borne by the different levels involved in RCAAP (RCAAP central level, participating institutions) and the users. On the benefits side, our analysis focused on the cost savings enabled by RCAAP, mainly thanks to the pooling of staff and resources generated by RCAAP. We acknowledge that some other types of benefits exist, notably facilitated access to scientific resources leading to time savings for users searching and downloading content. However, essential uncertainties in the collected data

²¹ Net Present Value (NPV) is a financial metric that calculates the difference between the costs and benefits for a project or investment, adjusted so that flows that happen at different points of time are comparable. A positive NPV indicates that the project is expected to be beneficial, while a negative NPV suggests it may not be worth pursuing.

preclude us from integrating this benefit into the analysis. As a result, we present findings that are quite conservative, though focusing on what we understand as the primary outcomes of RCCAP. Moreover, we also investigated other potential benefits such as time savings when uploading scientific content and training costs, but they cancel out between the counterfactual and real-world scenarios.

The following figure briefly presents the different types of costs and benefits, which will be discussed in the following sections. The costs mostly relate to the “Funding” input of the IPL (see section 2 above) and the benefits consist of cost savings identified as short-term outcomes in the IPL.

Figure 19. Costs and benefits covered by the CBA

Source: Authors. **Note:** Green: costs evaluated and cancelling out in the real-world and counterfactual scenarios; orange: costs confirmed as present but left out of the CBA due to uncertainties about savings.

3.1 Setting the analysis

The elements of the causal chain illustrated in the IPL require a thorough discussion in order to be translated into CBA elements. To ensure a comprehensive and relevant analysis of the costs and benefits of RCAAP, discussions of the following aspects were needed:

- Legal and functional boundaries of RCAAP
- Counterfactual scenario (What if RCAAP did not exist?),
- Population of users affected by the costs and benefits associated with RCAAP

Although these are common issues in a CBA analysis, their treatment is not straightforward when assessing an open science resource like RCAAP. In particular, the network and collaborative nature of the system, with several aggregated repositories and different

stakeholders contributing to its operations, implies a fragmentation of the available data. Some methodological assumptions were needed to frame the analysis effectively, drawing on discussions with the RCAAP team (University of Minho and FCCN) and insights gathered from the users' survey, interviews with repository managers and the focus group. These assumptions are briefly outlined in what follows.

3.1.1 Scope of the analysis

As mentioned above, the scope of the analysis will focus on the **core of the RCAAP initiative, i.e., its network of IR and supporting infrastructures and services** (RCAAP Portal, horizontal and support services such as statistics, training, and Helpdesk). The functional unit is thus the storage and diffusion of scientific documents, which aligns with the primary objectives of RCAAP. It implies considering the costs and benefits of operating, managing, and maintaining RCAAP, including depositing documents. Benefits are mainly linked to avoiding duplication of costs and the greater visibility of Portuguese research allowed by RCAAP.

Data and journal hosting services are excluded from the scope for three main reasons. Firstly, they are at an earlier stage of development. Secondly, they target an entirely distinct purpose compared with the IR. In particular, the journal hosting service aims to provide a platform for peer-reviewing articles. In contrast, the IR can host materials already present in other journals to improve access and preservation. The functional unit is, therefore, quite different. Thirdly, the IR benefit from a specific legislative framework (i.e., mandatory deposit) in Portugal. The data hosting and journal hosting services do not benefit from such an approach, which alters researchers' upload incentives.

Regarding the timeframe of the analysis, setting adequate boundaries is also essential. The RCAAP project started quickly in 2006-2008, with set-up investments in that period. Interviews suggest rapid preparatory activities (mainly in 2008) to launch the system. The RCAAP project aggregated some early repositories that existed before 2008, but they would have been implemented without the project.

As an Information Technology project in the field of Research and Innovation, standards regarding the reference period are not fully set in the existing literature. Given its underlying characteristics (i.e., small investment costs, research-orientation...), it was chosen to apply the time horizon of research projects, as defined in the European Commission benchmark table²². Consequently, the considered period for the RCAAP CBA was set at 2006-2026, i.e., a standard 20-year period. A side benefit is that it implies a very short forecast period, as data could typically be collected up to 2023-2024. Usually, forecasts for 2025 and 2026 were computed to

²² See https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/studies/cba_guide.pdf

reflect stability in real costs and benefits. These two years allow a comprehensive assessment of the costs and benefits alongside the lifecycle for this type of project.

3.1.2 Counterfactual scenario

Following the CBA approach, the analysis was performed to compare the benefits obtained from exploiting RCAAP with its costs using an incremental approach. This approach entailed comparing two scenarios: the actual, real-world scenario with RCAAP that we can directly observe against the counterfactual scenario where RCAAP does not exist. This approach enabled us to pinpoint the hypothetical 'net' benefits generated by RCAAP.

This task is not straightforward in the context of RCAAP. It requires assumptions regarding the likely development and use of IR in Portugal without RCAAP and potential alternatives for both deposits and search/download of Portuguese scientific content. Given the fact that several types of documents are uploaded to the IR aggregated by RCAAP, it is likely that users would shift not to a single alternative but to a combination of different ones. Respondents in various contexts (e.g., interviews, focus group, informal exchanges) also had different views on the likely breadth and pace of development of IR in Portugal without RCAAP, especially for smaller institutions that may have had important resource constraints.

As a result, the retained counterfactual was built on the assumption that the objective would have been to maintain a similar level of service (digitalisation of scientific resources through IR even in the absence of RCAAP). This choice allows our analysis to focus on the specific benefits of RCAAP (especially pooling of resources) to achieve a minimal level of service in digitalising scientific resources. The development of IR, even in the absence of RCAAP, can moreover be justified on several grounds, including the development of open science policies and mandates and international comparisons. However, it should be noted that some institutions (especially the smallest ones) could have faced significant challenges to reach that end without RCAAP (see Box below for details). This specific counterfactual thus face limitations, and alternative ones may be developed in the future to assess RCAAP. In particular, the counterfactual focuses on institutions, and assumes a similar pace of development of repositories, which may be challenged.

Box 1 What if RCAAP did not exist?

RCAAP is a national-level initiative supported by a legislative framework for its development and uptake. However, some repositories existed before the RCAAP project (e.g., the University of Minho's repository). According to the interviewees and the general trends observed in the literature, it is credible (though debatable) that Portuguese institutions would have developed their IR even without RCAAP²³. However, it could have higher costs (no pooling of infrastructure, no free

²³ The case of smaller institutions is the most uncertain, as they would probably have lacked the resources to roll out the IR.

hosting service) and potentially fewer functionalities (though DSPACE would probably still have been the chosen technical solution for most repositories, as observed in other countries). Critically, without RCAAP, the Portuguese research hosted on these repositories would be less visible due to the lack of a Portal for aggregation. Implications in terms of costs and benefits notably concern the IR's creation and operation. Without RCAAP, Portuguese institutions would have had to dedicate their own resources to run servers and design, maintain and upgrade their IR. Significant savings due to pooling would have been lost.

Regarding the search and download of documents, a plurality of situations would have to be considered. As documented by the survey, other open-source means to access the targeted scientific content would likely have been dominant in the absence of RCAAP. However, paid platforms and other means (e.g., exchanges with colleagues via email requests) were also considered popular alternatives. The variety of the content accessible through RCAAP may explain this observed diversity, and the counterfactual cannot assume a single alternative but rather a blend of these options. A particular benefit of the RCAAP system is its compilation of all Portuguese Master's and PhD theses, which are not accessible easily in other alternatives. For this particular content, it is expected that the lack of RCAAP would result in a significant drop in the number of views, with potential consequences, for instance lower visibility for early career researchers, less efficiency for students completing their work, etc. For different outputs, the decline in visibility may be more moderate. This complexity makes it challenging to assess this benefit in the CBA quantitatively, so it will be discussed qualitatively.

Figure 20. Hypothetical counterfactuals of RCAAP for searching and downloading content

Source: Authors' elaboration on RCAAP user survey.

For the users making deposits, the implications of the counterfactual scenario are smaller. Indeed, the time spent by stakeholders to make these deposits would have been similar, as the deployed solutions (DSPACE or alternatives) would not have been significantly different. It is corroborated by the small/uncertain time savings identified in the survey).

Note: The Figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The alternatives were not presented as mutually exclusive. The sample size is 180.

Source: Authors based on survey results, interviews, and literature

3.1.3 Users' population

While the IPL treats the RCAAP user population as an implicit component of the causal chain, it is a key element in the CBA, as users are directly affected by the impacts arising from the use of this resource. The IPL primarily highlights the various types of impact—academic, economic, and societal—within which RCAAP users operate. In this section, we derive best estimates of the RCAAP users, taking into consideration the specific challenges of an open resource.

As documented above, the RCAAP system (including its Portal and component IR) is an open resource involving different types of users: people using it to search and download content and those performing deposits to the repositories. While depositing files requires creating an account, searching and downloading content can be performed by any Internet user on the go. Moreover, the information is fragmented between multiple different Institutional Repositories.

This situation makes the estimation of the users' population challenging. In practice, it relies on different sources of information, including Google Analytics (volume of web traffic for people searching and downloading content) and internal DSpace statistics (number of downloads, numbers of accounts with deposit rights). Additionally, the recorded data may have specific limitations (e.g., risk of double-counting, robot activity), even though Google and RCAAP have already applied corrections to address these issues.

Consequently, the users' population can be assessed with margins of uncertainty (see Section 1.3. above for a full discussion of this issue). **For users searching and downloading content**, our best estimate uses Google Analytics data from the RCAAP Portal, leading to about **160,000 unique users on a yearly basis in recent years** (average for 2017-2024).

Besides using RCAAP and its IR to search and download content, the Portuguese academic community is also mobilised to perform the deposits. Given the wide range of modalities for upload across the different institutions (see Section 1), obtaining a precise number of the relevant population is challenging. In theory, all active researchers and librarians may be candidates for deposits. In practice, interviews suggest that only a much smaller number should be considered. Based on data provided by FCCN, it can be estimated **that about 11,300 accounts held deposit rights in 2024**²⁴, though not all of them may actively engage in deposits.

²⁴ Data was provided for RCOMUM and 27 SARI Repositories. Data for other repositories was estimated using a simple linear regression using the number of hosted documents as the Independent variable.

3.2 Costs

Identifying the costs associated with RCAAP necessitates careful consideration due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders. The RCAAP system includes not only the central level (University of Minho / FCCN) but also the individual institutions (that face “provider” costs) and the community of users that perform various tasks, most notably the deposits to the IR (“user” costs).

In line with the methodological framework described by Delugas, Catalano, and Vignetti, 2023, we considered both the costs incurred by the providers (RCAAP and individual institutions operating the IR) and those incurred by the users (e.g., librarians, research support staff, scientists or the broader public).

As in any traditional CBA, we categorised the **provider costs** into set-up and operational costs. They are largely covered by the “funding” input of the IPL:

- **Set-up costs** refer to the initial expenses associated with planning, designing, and launching RCAAP—essentially everything required to get it off the ground (i.e., investments and operational expenditures linked to the project launch). These set-up costs are relevant for launching the RCAAP system and for aggregating individual repositories. LOCAL repositories face higher set-up costs than other types of repositories since they have to manage their own technical equipment. In contrast, SARI and RCOMUM repositories delegate these aspects to RCAAP. They also cover reinvestment costs during the life of the project.
- **Operational costs** encompass all expenditures connected to activities such as managing the repositories, performing training, and performing other support activities for researchers.

The **costs incurred by users** encompass the time spent acquiring the necessary skills to use RCAAP, contributing to its content by depositing files, sending related metadata, and accessing the content (searching and downloading the files). They include costs under the “funding” input of the IPL (notably those linked to the wages of librarians performing deposits) but not only (e.g., access costs borne by external users). To account for these costs, we assigned a monetary value to the time users invested in using RCAAP based on the users’ survey, data on the volume of activity, and interviews.

- In practice, the **training and deposit costs** cancel out in the scenario with RCAAP when compared to the counterfactual. Indeed, we consider that users would have had to

experience a similar training process and that deposit times would have been identical even in the absence of RCAAP²⁵.

- For the **access costs**, we could model the costs borne by users in real-world conditions but not estimate the counterfactual due to uncertainties in the data (i.e., survey data could not be exploited to that end). Consequently, we do not integrate these costs into the CBA; instead, we discuss the findings. It should be noted that this choice is conservative, given that access costs are expected to decline thanks to RCAAP. In summary, our CBA will bias downwards the results of RCAAP.

The Table below provides an overview of the different types of costs attributed to the RCAAP providers (i.e., RCAAP and the other institutions, with differences depending on the types of repositories) and users. More details about these costs and the approach used to measure them are provided below.

Table 2 Costs related to RCAAP

STAKEHOLDER INVOLVED	COST TYPE	CATEGORY
Provider – RCAAP Central level	Set-up costs (RCAAP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments and reinvestments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Intangible fixed assets ◦ Computer equipment and software • Staff costs and other expenditure
	Operational costs (RCAAP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff costs and related expenditure • Training costs • Travel costs • Dissemination • Funding to partner institutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Memberships (fees paid by FCT to institutions to which it participates for RCAAP, such as DSpace, the DOI agency, or the Confederation of Open Access Repositories) • Other expenses
Provider – Institutional level	Set-up costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments and reinvestments (only for LOCAL repositories) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Computer equipment and related costs • Staff costs and other expenditures (for all types of repositories) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Technical staff costs ◦ Administrative and management staff costs

²⁵ This can be justified by the fact that DSpace would probably have been used in most cases for repositories even in the absence of RCAAP. In the 2023 Survey by COAR (Shearer et al., 2023), DSpace was indeed the most commonly used solution across European repositories (41%). Moreover, alternatives to DSpace are likely to generate similar time spent for training and performing deposits. This interpretation is strengthened by the interviews and the results of the survey showing no to small time savings for deposits.

	Operational costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintenance and technical support staff costs (only LOCAL repositories) ○ Administration and management staff costs (all types of repositories) ○ Librarian curation and checks costs (all types of repositories)
Users	Training costs	<p>It refers to the time spent learning to use RCAAP and become an efficient user (specifically to perform deposits).</p> <p>Interviews and the survey suggest that training costs are marginal, especially those specific to RCAAP/IR (and not to, e.g., Open Science policies or generic guidelines to follow). In practice, these costs cancel out when compared to the counterfactual since they would occur also in absence of RCAAP.</p>
	Deposit costs	<p>It refers to the time spent uploading content to RCAAP (borne by researchers and librarians). Again, these costs cancel out when compared to the counterfactual.</p>
	Access costs	<p>It refers to the time spent accessing and downloading the content available on RCAAP. These costs were evaluated for the real-world scenario but could not be estimated for the counterfactual due to uncertainties regarding time savings. As a result, they are not integrated into the CBA model but are nevertheless discussed for contextualisation.</p>

Source: Authors

As described in Section 1, RCAAP is fed by researchers and librarians based on documents produced in different contexts (e.g., scientific publications, theses, conference proceedings, etc.).

For the purpose of our analysis, we adopted methodological choices to assess the costs based on this reality:

- (i) Past costs related to creating documents hosted by RCAAP IR are considered sunk costs²⁶. These costs represent investments that would have been made regardless of the existence of RCAAP (e.g., drafting of research papers). This choice has a significant implication on the final result but it is justified because the focus of the RCAAP initiative is not the creation of scientific content per se, but rather the provision of a facilitated access to this content.
- (ii) The current costs incurred by researchers and institutions to carry out and publish scientific studies and other documents – then uploaded to RCAAP IR - are considered

²⁶ A sunk cost is an expense that has already been incurred and cannot be recovered or altered by current or future actions.

sunk costs. While these costs are essential for creating the content available on RCAAP, they are not part of RCAAP's direct financial responsibilities. Researchers would still conduct their studies independently of RCAAP, meaning these costs would have been incurred regardless of the existence of RCAAP itself.

Therefore, the costs included in the CBA analysis are limited to those explicitly recorded in the RCAAP budget, the costs borne by other providers (i.e., institutions managing their IR aggregated by RCAAP), and the costs faced by the user community contributing to RCAAP, mainly through the deposit of documents.

Provider costs

Providers (RCAAP and institutions operating the IR) incur two types of costs: set-up and operational costs, described below.

SET-UP COSTS

Set-up costs refer to the expenses associated with establishing RCAAP and its component IR (including the SARI hosting service). It also covers **necessary reinvestments during the lifetime of the project**. It refers mainly to equipment, infrastructure, and software expenditure (for RCAAP and LOCAL repositories). Set-up costs also include staff costs needed to launch the system and the different repositories. Indeed, specific actions are required to design the repositories (including, e.g., their governance, scope and content, interaction with open science/access policies, and when it applies technical considerations).

The approach to model the provider set-up costs in the real-world scenario was differentiated depending on the considered level: RCAAP (central level) or individual institutions operating the repositories.

At the RCAAP central level, high-quality budgetary data has been available from the FCCN RCAAP unit since the project's launch in 2008. It was complemented with additional data related to preparatory works in 2006-2008, which was obtained following interviews with FCCN staff. This raw data was analysed and filtered to focus on costs within the scope of the CBA. Moreover, some reinvestment costs (e.g., server and related equipment) were not present in the FCCN RCAAP unit budget after 2012 since they were shifted to another RCAAP unit. In order not to neglect these costs (which would bias the estimates), we modelled reinvestments as 1/8th of the initial investments from that year onwards, increasing in line with inflation. This approach was based on assumed depreciation rates and server investment cycles and was validated based on exchanges with FCCN staff.

Set-up costs are also borne by institutions having IR, primarily if they choose to operate their repositories independently, i.e., without joining the SARI or RCOMUM hosting services proposed by RCAAP. In that case, institutions with LOCAL repositories face set-up costs related to servers and related expenditures, as well as technical staff. Some set-up costs are related to

the administration and management of the repositories during their launch year, and all types of repositories face these costs.

These set-up costs were estimated based on interviews with repository managers and the literature, especially on the experience of the University of Minho (Swan, Picarra, and Rodrigues, 2016). It included modelling based on reinvestment cycles for servers for local repositories and staff costs for all repositories (based on their time spent and wages). These costs occurred at different times depending on the creation dates of the repositories. These dates are considered to model the costs highlighted in the Figure below.

The graph below presents an overview of RCAAP's provider set-up costs, distinguishing the types of providers (RCAAP Central level and Institutional level). We estimate that **during the entire timeframe of the CBA (2006-2026), set-up costs - including reinvestments - amounted to a total of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 3 million**. These costs were borne principally by the institutions (about 66%) and then by RCAAP itself (about 33%). As expected, the costs are concentrated in the project's early years (more than half in 2006-2010). Peaks in later years correspond to the massive entry of new repositories (e.g., RCOMUM collections in 2013) or reinvestment cycles for servers (e.g., 2020).

Figure 21. Estimated set-up costs (including reinvestments) by provider in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, interviews with repository managers, and additional sources from the literature. **Note:** All data in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values. The figures correspond to the real-world scenario with RCAAP. Reinvestment costs are included.

In the scenario without RCAAP, the provider costs related to RCAAP obviously do not occur. By contrast, we model the development of the different repositories using the cost structure of LOCAL repositories (with some adjustments for small institutions that would have been part of RCOMUM collections). It leads to total set-up costs of about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 3.8 million for 2006-2026**.

OPERATIONAL COSTS

Operational costs encompass all expenditures required to run and maintain RCAAP and its IR after the initial set-up phase. The primary categories of these costs include salaries/wages, but they also consist of travel expenses, equipment, consumables, external work purchases, etc.

As for the set-up costs, we must distinguish between the operational costs borne by the RCAAP at the central level and by the institutions to operate their IR.

At the RCAAP level, data is available in a consolidated form since the project’s inception until 2023. It mainly consists of staff costs but also funding for specific activities, such as dissemination, support to partner organisations, etc. By convention, the operational costs begin in 2009. Prior costs (including staff ones) were assessed as linked to the design and launch of the system and thus counted as set-up costs.

There was no unified dataset for the operational costs at the institutional level. Moreover, institutions typically do not record a dedicated budget for their repositories. As a result, their costs were reconstructed based on interviews and survey data (Shearer, Nakano, and Rodrigues, 2023). Components of operational costs at this level include administrative and management costs, technical and maintenance costs (only for LOCAL repositories having their own servers) and librarian curation and checks costs (reviewing metadata and upload quality). All these costs are basically staff costs, which were estimated based on the time spent by workers fulfilling these tasks during the development of the different repositories. Cost profiles were derived for every type of repository (LOCAL, SARI, RCOMUM) to ensure that their specificities were considered. These cost profiles use the number of FTE and related wages of workers involved in the different tasks, with a gradual rise to account for the development of repositories over time. For instance, the figure below outlines the cost profile of administrative and management staff for LOCAL repositories by age of the repository.

Figure 22. Operational Costs profile for LOCAL Repositories – Administrative and Management costs by age of repository

Source: Authors based on interviews with repository managers and wage data (Payscale). **Note:** All data in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values. Graph starts from second year (since the first year of the repository is considered set-up).

The Figure below provides an overview of the total computed operational costs²⁷. We estimate that during the entire timeframe of the CBA (2006-2026), **operational provider costs amounted to a total of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 34.5 million**. The vast majority (91%) occurred at the institutional level. In 2024, operational costs reached a yearly value of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 2.5 million. These costs rose substantially over time due to the development of the repositories (increasing number over time) and the maturity of the repositories, implying more resource use.

Figure 23. Estimated operational costs by provider in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, interviews with repository managers, and additional sources from the literature. **Note:** For the RCAAP level, all operational expenditures were collected from the budget, aggregating the relevant categories (see Table 2 above). For the institutions' level, expenditure was estimated based on the time spent by the staff involved in administrative/management, curation/checks and maintenance activities. Time spent is calculated based on interviews and external data. Time spent was valorised using the gross wages of university librarians/staff in Portugal (Payscale data). Data does not include deposit costs. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

In the scenario without RCAAP, the operational costs related to RCAAP obviously do not occur, similarly to the set-up costs. For the LOCAL repositories, the operational costs do not change. However, institutions that choose SARI or RCOMUM hosting services would have to operate their own repositories and thus face a similar cost structure to the LOCAL ones. We model this

²⁷ This estimate does not include deposit costs, even if they are borne by librarians. These costs are part of users' costs. However, the operational costs cover the checks and curation work performed by librarians to ensure the quality of the content of their IR.

process (with some adjustments for small institutions that would have been part of RCOMUM collections). It leads to total operational costs of about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 35.5 million for 2006-2026** (slightly higher than with RCAAP), or about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 2.8 million in 2024**.

Users' costs

Users' costs refer to the expenses incurred when dealing with different RCAAP-related actions, such as learning to use the system (and its component IR), performing deposits or searching and accessing content indexed on RCAAP. Including these costs in the model is crucial to avoid overestimating the benefits users derive from the system. These costs can be divided into three main categories:

- A. **Training costs:** Time spent learning how to use RCAAP. It refers to the time spent by people attending these training sessions in individual institutions to perform deposits on the IR (mainly researchers). According to the survey and qualitative evidence, these costs are minimal as the complex issues are linked to overarching principles (e.g., metadata guidelines and legal considerations...) rather than the RCAAP system itself. They are modelled but cancel out in the real-world and counterfactual scenarios.
- B. **Deposit costs:** Time dedicated to actively uploading content to the repositories aggregated by RCAAP. Portuguese researchers or librarians performing the upload on their behalf (depending on the practices and policies of each institution) bear these costs. As for the training costs, deposit costs are cancelling out in the counterfactual scenario when compared to the real-world scenario because we expect that the alternative system would use the same (or similar) software, leading to insignificant changes in time spent by users for that end.
- C. **Accessing costs:** Time spent accessing RCAAP resources through the Portal, the IR, or other channels. They are borne by all the users using RCAAP to search and download content (academic users and beyond). These costs are modelled in the real-world scenario with RCAAP, but they could not be assessed for the counterfactual scenario. Indeed, time gains were too challenging for users to estimate, leading to survey data inconsistencies. As a result, these costs are not included in the CBA results but are still discussed. As mentioned above, we clearly expect time savings for access costs, so excluding them is a conservative approach to assessing the project.

From a cost-benefit analysis perspective, the time invested in these activities represents an opportunity cost. While it does not involve direct financial expenditure, it reflects the value of time that could have been devoted to alternative tasks. The following sections detail how these costs were collected and how their monetary value was estimated and incorporated into the CBA (excluding access costs).

A. TRAINING COSTS

The first type of user cost relates to the time spent learning to navigate and use the repositories aggregated by RCAAP, focusing on making deposits to the IR²⁸. Evidence from the interviews and the survey suggests overall that it is relatively straightforward to grasp the system, as highlighted by small differences in time spent for first use of the system compared to typical use (see Figure below). Indeed, the median user spends about 5-10 minutes in both cases, but higher values are overrepresented for the first user (e.g., 6% for 30 min – 1h. against 4% for typical use). This pattern suggests a relatively small need for training sessions.

Figure 24. Comparison of time spent by users to make a deposit on RCAAP-aggregated IR in first use and typical use

Source: Authors based on RCAAP survey. **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents' percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 82 respondents performing deposits on one (or more) IR aggregated by RCAAP.

However, advanced users, especially librarians and related staff tend to point out that there is a learning curve to absorb the different rules related to the uploads. The more complex rules are mainly associated with the various policies and procedures related to the uploads rather than to the act of performing the deposits themselves.

Even if using DSpace to perform deposits is usually not considered complex²⁹, the different institutions operating the IR can propose training sessions, targeting users such as students and researchers. These sessions are typically organised by librarians and often bundle issues related to RCAAP and the IR with broader considerations about open science, specific resources, etc.

²⁸ Training opportunities are also proposed by the RCAAP central level, though this offer mainly targets librarians and repository managers. These costs are thus counted in the operational costs of the system, rather than as user costs.

²⁹ Though there are differences depending on the IT skills of researchers, especially for older generations.

The costs for the institutions are covered in the provider costs (under operational expenditure). Still, there is also a cost for users, i.e., the value of the time they spend attending these training sessions.

As discussed above, the training costs will cancel out in the counterfactual scenario instead of the real-world scenario. Thus, they do not impact the net benefit brought by RCAAP. However, we still provide an estimate of these costs for reference. It should be noted that these costs are minimal but with some uncertainties due to the critical variable of the number of persons benefiting from training sessions each year. Indeed, no data is directly available for the number of attendees. We thus rely on an estimate based on the number of accounts with deposit rights and a correction factor (25%, arbitrary). We know from interviews with repository managers and librarians that typical training sessions last about 1 hour. Based on wage estimates of the attendees (weighted by their roles observed in the RCAAP survey), we can estimate the value of one hour of their time. **The cost of training one user is evaluated at about EUR₂₀₂₄ 12.** By multiplying this value by the number of attendees (about 280 per year in the last years), we derive the total training costs on a yearly basis. **This calculation implies that the total user cost for training is, at most, in the thousands of euros, with a preferred yearly estimate of EUR₂₀₂₄ 3,500 in 2024.**

B. DEPOSIT COSTS

Deposit costs refer to the time and effort users invest in uploading content to the IR aggregated by RCAAP. These include time to transfer the files, compile the metadata, and check the information. From a CBA perspective, deposits require a certain level of effort, expertise, and user resources that could have been allocated to other tasks. Therefore, these costs are considered an opportunity cost. They are not limited to the initial phase of using RCAAP, as they occur on a rolling basis throughout its usage. Consequently, they are part of the operating costs.

Both researchers and librarians perform deposits on their behalf. According to interviews and the evidence from the survey, librarians make a substantial share of deposits (20-50%, depending on the context). For these deposits, the costs are evaluated based on the time librarians dedicate to them, valorised using their gross wages (similar to other operational costs, see above). For deposits performed by researchers, the cost is estimated based on the number of deposits, the time spent by the researcher per deposit (based on the survey – see Figure below), and the gross wage of Portuguese researchers (Payscale data). The time needed to perform a single deposit is relatively small, **with the median user falling in the 5-10 minutes range** (see Figure below). Researchers typically spend less time on deposits than librarians.

Figure 25. Time spent to upload a piece of content to the IR by function

Source: Authors based on RCAAP survey (sample size: administrators = 33, researchers = 36). **Note:** The Figure shows the percentage distribution mode of respondents. The sample is composed of users making deposits on one or more IR aggregated by RCAAP. Its size is 33 (administrators) or 36 (researchers).

Based on these assumptions, we can estimate the deposit costs the users (librarians and researchers) bear. **The cost of a deposit by librarians is estimated at EUR₂₀₂₄ 1,9; for a researcher, this figure reaches EUR₂₀₂₄ 3.2.** By multiplying these unit costs by the number of yearly deposits (for each type of users), we obtain the total deposit costs induced by the network of RCAAP repositories. As the number of deposits grows over time, so does the cost (see Figure below).

Figure 26. Estimated deposit costs by type of users in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, Payscale data, interviews with repository managers, and RCAAP survey.

Note: Costs were derived using the number of deposits to RCAAP and the unit costs of a single deposit. The number of deposits was estimated from RCAAP data on the number of aggregated documents on the system (corrected for journal articles). Time spent for a single deposit was calculated based on interviews and RCAAP survey data. Time spent was valorised using the gross wages of university librarians/researchers in Portugal (Payscale data). All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

We estimate that **during the entire timeframe of the CBA (2006-2026), deposit costs amounted to a total of about EUR₂₀₂₄ 3.2 million.** The majority (82%) was borne by researchers due to a higher share of total deposits and higher average wages when compared to librarians. In 2024, operational costs reached a yearly value of about **EUR₂₀₂₄ 270,000.** These costs rose substantially over time due to the development of the repositories (increasing number over time) and the maturity of the repositories, implying more resource use.

However, as for the training costs, **these costs are expected to cancel out since the counterfactual scenario implies a similar development and burden for users when compared to the real-world scenario with RCAAP.** Thus, deposit costs do not drive RCAAP's net benefits.

C. ACCESS COSTS

The last type of user cost relates to the time spent accessing and downloading documents from the IR aggregated by RCAAP in various ways (directly through the IR, through the RCAAP Portal or through other search engines, for instance). As mentioned above, these costs were evaluated for the real-world scenario with RCAAP. Still, they could not be assessed for the counterfactual scenario due to the difficulties respondents/interviewees had in imagining this situation and the potential consequences it would have had for their work. As a consequence, we present the figures for the total access costs for the scenario with RCAAP (to show that they are significant) but do not include them in the CBA. This choice is conservative, as it is expected that RCAAP lowers these costs relative to the counterfactual.

The time invested in accessing documents was collected during the RCAAP user survey. The data gathered indicates that user responses are predominantly concentrated in the shortest time ranges, with less than 10 minutes typically required to access the documents, regardless of the access method (See Figure below).

Figure 27. Time spent by RCAAP users to search and download content by access modality

Source: Authors based on RCAAP survey **Note:** The Figure shows the respondents’ percentage distribution mode. The sample comprises 101 respondents searching and downloading content through the RCAAP Portal, and 87 through Institutional Repositories.

We use this time spent as well as the frequency of use (also collected during the survey) to derive the total time spent by users accessing RCAAP documents. To express the value of the time invested in accessing RCAAP documents in monetary terms, we then used the GDP per capita equivalent for the time spent as a proxy. GDP per capita was used because the occupational composition of people who search and read content is not robustly known. We weighted the GDP per capita by the countries of origin of readers, which are known thanks to RCAAP Google Analytics statistics.

Overall, these costs were estimated to be less than EUR₂₀₂₄330 million for the entire considered period (2006-2026). **This is a significant cost that rises in line with the development of the system. In recent years, access costs amounted to about EUR₂₀₂₄ 20 million (e.g., in 2024).**

This should be considered as a lower bound estimate, given that it relies on the assumption of about 160,000 yearly users.

Figure 28. Estimated access costs in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on RCAAP data, RCAAP survey, OECD, IMF and ECB. **Note:** The number of accesses to search and download content was first estimated using the number of yearly unique users and their frequency of uses. This number was then converted to time spent accessing content using the relevant question of the survey. Once this total time spent was obtained, it was converted to monetary values by multiplying by the value of time. This value of time was derived from the weighted GDP per capita of the countries of users. Data in US dollars was converted to EUR. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

In the RCAAP survey, we explored the additional time that users would have spent accessing documents without RCAAP. However, the difficulties in imagining this scenario, as well as the structure of the question (asking for time savings on a weekly basis), resulted in inconsistent and implausible findings. There was a major risk of misestimating the access cost savings of RCAAP, which is why we decided to adopt the conservative decision to exclude access costs from the CBA model. Indeed, since we expect access costs to be reduced thanks to RCAAP compared to the counterfactual, the exclusion of access costs (and related net savings) from the model means that RCAAP's benefits are a lower bound in our CBA.

Overview of total costs

By combining all the available costs to run the system in the real-world scenario (except for users' access costs), we reached **about EUR₂₀₂₄ 41 million (2006-2026)**. Costs rise with time due to the development of the different IR, and in the final years, **the yearly costs amount to about EUR₂₀₂₄ 2.8 million (2024)**.

Figure 29. Overview of total costs in the real-world scenario with RCAAP (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on previous graphs (multiple sources). **Note:** Total costs include all providers (RCAAP Central level and Institutional level), as well as the users. Access costs are excluded. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

Providers' operational costs constitute the great majority of the total costs to ensure the service (85%). The central level accounts for about 9% of these operational costs, while institutions bear the bulk of them.

3.3 Benefits

As discussed in Section 2, the short-term benefits of RCAAP primarily consist of costs saved thanks to the pooling of resources allowed by the system to reach a similar level of service without RCAAP³⁰. Institutions would face higher costs, particularly regarding infrastructure/equipment and personnel. In line with the CBA open science framework described by Delugas et al. (2023), we identified two types of benefits associated with RCAAP that could be incorporated into the entire CBA:

- (i) The time saved in streamlining and pooling resources for the launch and operation of the different repositories. It includes savings regarding administration/management and technical aspects (**labour cost savings**).

³⁰ These cost savings are benefits because they correspond to the gains for institutions allowed by RCAAP. By contrast, the costs of RCAAP refer to the additional costs linked to the emergence and operation of the system (at the central level). This presentation ensures that no double-counting is performed.

- (ii) The time saved in pooling resources for the technical infrastructures of the IR, in particular, the use of shared servers provided by RCAAP to the institutions. (***data storage costs savings***)

Some benefits highlighted in the IPL were investigated but not integrated into the CBA for different motives:

- **Some benefits were either too uncertain or too small to be integrated into the model.**
 - They notably included the internal benefits of having access to RCAAP from the point of view of institutions. For instance, RCAAP provides statistics through a dedicated add-on for librarians. These statistics can be used for different purposes, such as monitoring scientific activity and drafting internal reports.
 - Similarly, the evidence from IR can be used to evaluate researchers (e.g., career evaluation based on the deposited documents). However, additional interviews with the repository managers suggested that the efficiency gains from these possibilities were small and difficult to attribute solely to RCAAP (as opposed to having an IR, which would happen under the counterfactual scenario).
 - As explained above, costs were considered equal under the real-world and counterfactual scenarios for training and deposit costs. As a result, they do not produce any savings and are not included in this section on benefits.
- **Some benefits were clearly present but not assessable with the available evidence.**
 - It included the benefits connected to the effects of RCAAP on access to documents (e.g., a higher number of downloads, reduced access costs in terms of time spent – for instance, for PhD theses...). The difficulty of having a clear counterfactual in mind for the respondents (of the survey and interviews) and to model these trends made the inclusion of these benefits too uncertain. This can bring valuable lessons for future research (see below).
 - In particular, we investigated access cost savings (in terms of potential time savings), but as outlined in the previous section, we could not integrate them robustly into the model. Benefits from access cost savings are expected to be significant, so our results should be analysed with that methodological choice in consideration, i.e., as a lower bound of the true benefits of RCAAP.

The cost savings forming the benefits of RCAAP are relevant for SARI repositories and RCOMUM collections. Indeed, LOCAL repositories face significant labour and equipment costs to store their data, since they do not join the shared hosting services RCAAP provides. Consequently, to incorporate the savings in the cost-benefit analysis, we applied the cost structure of LOCAL repositories (e.g., equipment costs, personnel costs) to institutions that chose SARI or RCOMUM under the real-world scenario. To consider that RCOMUM institutions are smaller, we applied a correction ratio (25% based on observed downloads when compared to LOCAL repositories,

i.e., a proxy of activity) to not overstate the potential benefits. The cost structure of LOCAL repositories was retrieved thanks to interviews with repository managers and findings from the literature.

RCAAP allows cost savings for the institutions adopting SARI or RCOMUM repositories. It implies that the difference in costs for institutional providers between the counterfactual and RCAAP scenario are counted as benefits in the results section (i.e., the difference in costs is net savings). This allows the analysis to avoid double-counting issues (see Section 3.4. for further details).

In the subsections below, we provide a more detailed explanation of the rationale for including these provider cost savings in our analysis, along with their estimation results. They are composed of labour cost savings and data storage cost savings.

Labour cost savings

Labour cost savings occur for SARI and RCOMUM repositories. From the perspective of institutions having SARI/RCOMUM repositories, labour cost savings arise from two distinct channels:

- Some tasks simply do not exist for them in this arrangement, as compared to the counterfactual of operating its own repositories (LOCAL cost structure). In particular, technical and maintenance staff do not have to be employed (or contracted as external providers) by institutions joining SARI/RCOMUM. Instead, technical staff managing their repositories is pooled and shared at the RCAAP central level. By splitting their time across several repositories, RCAAP employees at the central level are more efficient than several workers in each institution.
- Some other tasks are simplified in this arrangement, as compared to the counterfactual of operating its own repositories (LOCAL cost structure). It includes simplified management and administrative tasks (since the process is standardised through the service provided by RCAAP), librarians' checks and curation, etc.

The savings were estimated based on the working time (in full-time equivalent) for these different activities between LOCAL and other types of repositories. For instance, managing and administrating a mature SARI repository is estimated at 1.35 FTE against 1.5 FTE for a LOCAL repository (i.e., a yearly saving of 0.15 FTE). The FTE were then monetised using wages for the different occupations (based on Payscale data) to compute the savings.

The following Figure outlines the evolution of labour cost savings over time. The savings only materialise after introducing operational SARI (and RCOMUM) repositories, i.e., from 2009 onwards. The savings rise with the development of these repositories.

Figure 30. Labour costs savings for providers (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources, and interviews with repository managers. **Note:** Labour cost savings correspond to savings for institutions with SARI/RCOMUM repositories compared to the counterfactual with the LOCAL repositories' cost structure. These labour cost savings notably include technical/maintenance, administrative/management, and curation/check staff. Costs are scaled for repositories of the RCOMUM type due to their small size (25%). All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

Overall, **labour cost savings can be estimated at about EUR₂₀₂₄ 5 million for 2006-2026. In recent years, they have reached about EUR₂₀₂₄ 365,000 on a yearly basis.** These savings must obviously be balanced against the costs borne at the RCAAP central level to provide the shared hosting services.

Data storage cost savings

Data storage cost savings associated with RCAAP refer to the costs avoided by providers due to the existence of hosting services (SARI/RCOMUM), eliminating the need to store data locally or on other systems. While these costs are relatively small compared to labour costs, they are still significant, particularly because regular updates are needed. The literature and interviews suggest that replacement cycles every 5-10 years are credible for the IR servers hosting scientific documents.

Since institutions using SARI/RCOMUM do not have servers at all under their arrangement, the savings simply correspond to the avoided costs of the servers (initial investments and reinvestments). We thus modelled these costs in the same way as we did for the LOCAL repositories. As for the labour costs, we applied a corrective factor (25%, based on the observed number of downloads) to the RCOMUM institutions since their small scope would probably require small servers as well. This approach is considered conservative, i.e., it probably leads to lower RCAAP benefits than in reality.

The following Figure shows the trend in data storage cost savings over time. The savings feature significant year-on-year variations, which are due to the different creation dates of the repositories, and to the length of the reinvestment cycles.

Figure 31. Data storage costs savings for providers (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources, and interviews with repository managers. **Note:** Data storage cost savings are estimated based on the costs of servers observed for LOCAL repositories (initial investments, reinvestments). Costs are scaled for repositories of the RCOMUM type due to their small size (25%). All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

Overall, **data storage cost savings can be estimated at about EUR₂₀₂₄ 940,000 for 2006-2026.** As for labour cost savings, these savings must be contrasted with the costs borne by RCAAP at the central level to store documents on behalf of beneficiary institutions.

Overview of total benefits

Combining the two different types of benefits, we observe that we reach an undiscounted value³¹ of almost **EUR₂₀₂₄ 6 million for 2006-2026.** The Figure below shows these benefits materialised a few years after RCAAP and its component repositories were launched. Moreover, the savings in labour costs are much higher than the savings in data storage costs, though the latter are still significant (about 15% of the total). In recent years, **benefits amount to about EUR₂₀₂₄ 470,000 yearly (2024).**

³¹ Undiscounted value does not account for the fact that the same amount of costs and benefits can be worth less in the future when compared to today. It simply aggregates all expected benefits and costs over a period, without applying any correction. To account for the fact that benefits and costs are worth more today than in the future, we can apply a Social Discount Rate (SDR) to undiscounted values. Thanks to the SDR, we can convert all costs and benefits to make sure their values are comparable, as of today.

Figure 32. Overview of total benefits for providers (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources, and interviews with repository managers. **Note:** Total benefits for providers include labour cost savings and data storage cost savings. As noted above, access cost savings are not considered. All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

The following section compiles costs and benefits consistently to avoid double-counting and deliver a final judgment on the performance of RCAAP.

3.4 Overall results

This section combines the different costs and benefits consistently analysed in the CBA model. More precisely, it compares the costs and benefits of the real-world scenario with RCAAP against the counterfactual scenario without RCAAP but with an emerging IR network sharing the same cost structure as LOCAL repositories.

As we have retrieved and modelled investment costs, it is possible to derive key metrics of performance for the CBA, including the Net Present Value and the project's benefit-cost ratio³².

The costs presented in this section correspond to the costs borne by RCAAP at the central level. Indeed, these costs do not exist in the scenario without RCAAP, so the difference with the counterfactual is the actual costs. Institutional provider costs are not included since they cancel out for LOCAL repositories (same situation with and without RCAAP), and they are counted as

³² As noted above, Net Present Value (NPV) is a financial metric that calculates the difference between the costs and benefits for a project or investment, adjusted so that flows that happen at different points of time are comparable. A positive NPV indicates that the project is expected to be beneficial, while a negative NPV suggests it may not be worth pursuing.

A benefit-cost ratio is simply Net Benefits divided by Net Costs. A ratio greater than 1 implies that benefits outweigh costs. A ratio lower than 1 implies the contrary.

cost savings and, hence, as benefits for SARI/RCOMUM. This choice ensures that we do not experience double-counting problems. Finally, the users' costs are not included since they cancel out for deposits and training costs and could not be included for access costs (see below). Symmetrically, no access cost savings are included as benefits.

As a result, the benefits include the cost savings described in Section 3.3. Since we do not include access cost savings (which are likely significant), we provide a very conservative estimate for RCAAP benefits. As we will show, the project is a net social gain even under these unfavourable assumptions.

The benefits and costs do not materialise simultaneously, given the preparatory activities and the set-up of both RCAAP and its aggregated repositories. Accordingly, we can observe that the net benefit is negative until 2014 (benefits appear by 2009 but do not offset the costs until 2014). At the end of the period (2020s onwards), we reach yearly net benefits in the realm of EUR₂₀₂₄ 300,000.

Figure 33. Net benefits over time (2006-2026)

Source: Authors based on multiple data sources. **Note:** All data is in real (2024 euros) undiscounted values.

To adequately take into consideration the fact that benefits and costs do not occur at the same time, we apply a social discount rate to all values. Indeed, the value of one euro is not the same across time. This discount rate results in higher weight being given to the project's early years (as opposed to later years). **The Table below summarises the estimated costs and running benefits for RCAAP over the entire reference period (2006-2026).** We discount the values from different years using a standard rate obtained from the literature (Catalano et al., 2022).

A few important considerations arise from these results:

- Personnel costs incurred by the RCAAP central level account for a significant share (about 56%) of the expenses required to launch and operate this resource. This category

also accounts for the personnel providing the benefits to participating institutions (which do not have to employ, e.g., IT technicians to run their own repositories)

- Labour cost savings are the most substantial benefits considered in this analysis, while data storage costs are much less marginal. Labour cost savings derive from the greater efficiency of sharing experienced personnel, resulting in economies of scale.
- By comparing the estimated costs and benefits associated with RCAAP, it is evident that the benefits significantly outweigh the costs under this counterfactual. **Specifically, the net present value of the entire system amounts to EUR₂₀₂₄ 1.1 million. More intuitively, it means that the system results in benefits that are at least 32% larger than costs (focusing on the cost savings due to the pooling of resources).**
- Moreover, this estimate does not include access cost savings, i.e., the fact that users spend less time searching and downloading content with RCAAP as opposed to the counterfactual. **If we considered this benefit, the results of RCAAP would be even higher.**

Table 3 Overview of results for RCAAP

results (EUR 2024)	DISCOUNTED VALUE (2006-2026)	UNDISCOUNTED VALUE (2006-2026)
<i>TOTAL COSTS (A)</i>	3,559,370	4,206,054
<i>Total set-up costs (RCAAP central level), of which:</i>	930,517	1,041,018
<i>Intangible fixed assets</i>	1,581	1,797
<i>Computer equipment and software</i>	592,102	696,344
<i>Operational costs for set-up</i>	336,833	342,877
<i>Total operational costs (RCAAP central level), of which:</i>	2,628,853	3,165,037
<i>Staff costs and related expenditure</i>	1,675,444	2,005,700
<i>Training costs</i>	6,145	7,538
<i>Travel costs</i>	40,553	50,041
<i>Dissemination</i>	29,115	31,062
<i>Funding to partner institutions</i>	142,334	186,023
<i>Other expenses</i>	735,262	884,672
<i>Total USER costs (EUR), of which:</i>	N/A	N/A
<i>Training costs</i>	N/A	N/A
<i>Deposits costs</i>	N/A	N/A
<i>Access costs</i>	Not included	
<i>TOTAL BENEFITS (B), of which</i>	4,689,963	5,992,536
<i>Labor costs savings</i>	3,937,893	5,053,289
<i>Data storage cost savings</i>	752,070	939,247
<i>Access costs savings</i>	Not included	
NET PRESENT VALUE (B - A)	1,130,594	
BENEFIT COST RATIO (B / A)	1.32	

Source: Authors' elaboration on multiple sources (see previous sections). **Note:** The Table reports the values for the 2006-2026 period. All values are expressed in real (2024 euros) values. Discounted values used the baseline estimate of Catalano et al. for Portugal (1.97%).

It is challenging to compare our results to the broader scientific literature since a fully-fledged CBA of IR / networks of IR was not available to the best of our knowledge. Previous studies (e.g., Burns et al., 2013) tended to confirm our results regarding costs borne by individual repositories, but the evidence on the benefits side (e.g., access costs savings) remains scarce. Evidence from the focus group and the interviews contributed to validating the results, albeit qualitatively. In particular, the contributors stressed the importance of RCAAP in pooling resources and allowing the development of IR in Portugal, especially for smaller institutions³³. They also noted that easy access to resources was an advantage, which we could not include in the CBA but could be highlighted in further research.

4. Benefits beyond CBA

As shown in the RCAAP IPL (see Section 2), the benefits of RCAAP go beyond short-term outcomes, such as cost savings measured through the cost-benefit analysis. Instead, these benefits reach further, encompassing what we have identified in the IPL as long-term outcomes. Although these outcomes are linked to the use of RCAAP, their occurrence also depends on additional user effort and resources, making it challenging to attribute them solely to RCAAP, unlike the short-term outcomes. It includes cultural, economic or organisational benefits (e.g., creating new entrepreneurial ideas and cultural diffusion). The common feature of these benefits is that they are challenging to observe.

Overall, the evidence on these benefits is limited, and the data points towards relatively modest effects at this stage.

Anecdotes from the interviewees suggested that the wider society could benefit from RCAAP in the form of increase knowledge or culture. For instance, a repository manager noted that there were some recorded cases where patients with specific medical conditions would find relevant content on their diseases on the IR and even contact the researchers on that basis. However, these long-term outcomes remained rare (even if probably under-counted) and the causal attribution to RCAAP uncertain.

When it comes to improved research productivity in Portugal, data from the University of Minho (Work Package 3) shows that the total output of Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR forms a significant share of the total Portuguese scientific outputs. Indeed, about 40% of the total number of Portuguese scientific documents is hosted on RCAAP IR (see Figure).

³³ In some cases, they mentioned that they believed that without RCAAP, IR would maybe not have developed, or at the same pace in Portugal. In our counterfactual, we hypothesised that this development occurred in order to compare similar levels of services.

Figure 34. Number of Portuguese scientific documents by presence on RCAAP (2015-2024)

Source: Authors based on WP3 (University of Minho). **Note:** RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR. Non-RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents not hosted on RCAAP IR.

However, documents hosted on RCAAP IR receive much less citations than those non-hosted on RCAAP, about half as much in the mid-2010s (citations tend to be less reliable in the most recent years due to the time lag between publications and citations). Moreover, the ratio of RCAAP to non-RCAAP citations tends to decline, casting doubts on the ability of RCAAP to boost visibility of research.

Figure 35. Mean Citations per Document depending on presence on RCAAP (2015-2024)

Source: Authors based on WP3 (University of Minho). **Note:** RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR. Non-RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents not hosted on RCAAP IR.

However, this data is purely correlational and does not allow a direct attribution of causality to RCAAP (in particular, because non-RCAAP documents may be positively selected, e.g., more represented in prestigious journals under paywalls). A boost of visibility may still be present

thanks to RCAAP, and we can hypothesise that it may notably be relevant for documents published in less visible journals, or other types of documents that would not benefit from significant exposure otherwise (e.g., theses).

Industry-academia collaborations are another form of long-term potential outcome of RCAAP. In this realm, data from Work Package 3 / University of Minho can also be used. Indeed, it is possible to track the number of documents involving both academic and industrial stakeholders over time, distinguishing RCAAP and non-RCAAP documents. As shown in the Figure below, few documents (on RCAAP or on other venues) refer to industry-academia collaborations in Portugal.

Figure 36. Share of Portuguese scientific documents with industry-academia collaboration by presence on RCAAP (2015-2024)

Source: Authors based on WP3 (University of Minho). **Note:** RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents hosted on RCAAP IR. Non-RCAAP refers to Portuguese scientific documents not hosted on RCAAP IR.

More critically, documents hosted on RCAAP are less linked to industry-academia collaborations than those not hosted on RCAAP (about 3 times less chance). Due to differences in composition of the RCAAP and non-RCAAP sample, we cannot exclude that RCAAP may promote some industry-academia collaborations, but there is no firm evidence to support that view. Regardless, the absolute effect would be very small, confirming that the core of RCAAP’s benefits is not economic, but rather academic.

5. Conclusions and lessons learned

5.1 Conclusions

This case study aimed to test the cost-benefit analysis framework described by Delugas et al. (2023) to assess open science projects and practices. We relied on a comprehensive set of qualitative and quantitative methods for data collection and analysis to carry out this analysis. Primary data on costs and usage were obtained from the RCAAP team, repository managers and researchers, while user information was gathered through a user survey. Additional qualitative insights emerged from numerous interviews and a focus group conducted throughout the analysis, which helped validate our findings.

The analysis started with the construction of the impact pathways framework of RCAAP - based on Dekker, Karasz et al. (2023)—to illustrate how the funding and resources provided to RCAAP (inputs) lead to direct benefits (outputs and outcomes) and drive advancements (impacts) in science, (and to a much lesser extent) the economy, and society. This allowed us to identify both short- and long-term outcomes, as well as broader socio-economic impacts, associated with RCAAP and sketch the main RCAAP Impact Pathways.

The CBA was explicitly applied to evaluate the short-term outcomes RCAAP provides – especially to its participating institutions. However, a broader causal pathways analysis was used to assess long-term outcomes, acknowledging that these outcomes often involve multiple contributing factors, making it difficult to establish a direct causal link to RCAAP. Precisely, RCAAP's long-term outcomes were tracked through qualitative evidence sources, including interviews and user surveys.

It was possible to carry out a full assessment of set-up and operational costs for RCAAP, and thus to derive its Net Present Value. However, it was not possible to integrate all relevant costs/benefits into the model, with the significant case being access costs (savings). This fact should be taken into consideration when reviewing the results. Critically, this issue biases the analysis downwards. **Our baseline estimate suggests that the benefits of RCAAP are 32% higher than its costs, and these benefits would likely significantly rise by considering access cost savings. Our analysis also considers a counterfactual that is not a closed science alternative, but rather an unintegrated approach to open science (i.e., development of IR of Portuguese stakeholders without networking and pooling of resources).** Alternative scenarios would have produced different estimates.

With these caveats highlighted, the following findings shall be stressed:

- **Structure of providers' costs:** The network of IR organised around RCAAP is characterised by the importance of labour costs and the prominence of costs at the level of individual institutions (as opposed to the RCAAP central level). This particular cost structure can be contrasted to several projects in the field of R&D but is consistent with ICT-based projects and the existing literature on IR (see, e.g., Burns et al., 2013).
- **User Costs:** The functioning of RCAAP is based upon actions realized by its users, either to deposit or to search for content in its different IR. These costs include training, deposit and access costs. It is clear that the dominant cost is related to access, given the volume and time spent on this aspect. However, it is also challenging to evaluate, especially when it comes to assessing the counterfactual.
- **Cost savings:** The primary short-term benefits of RCAAP consist of cost savings to the institutions benefiting from shared hosting services. These savings included personnel costs (i.e., less time spent for workers to manage the IR) and infrastructure/equipment (data storage savings). Labour cost savings were the most significant. These savings originate from the greater efficiency in pooling some resources at the central level (e.g., economies of scale...) compared to each institution operating independently.
- **Net Benefit Justification:** The cost-benefit analysis results indicate that RCAAP's net benefit exceeds the expenditure required to launch, maintain and operate it. Specifically, benefits are at least 32% higher than costs, and this ratio would favourably improve if access cost savings were integrated into the model.

Beyond the short-term outcomes, RCAAP may have a positive role in accelerating scientific research, especially in Portugal but also abroad. By facilitating access to scientific resources, further research, results uptake and diffusion could be boosted. However, the scale of these benefits is difficult to assess, given the potential alternative routes to access the content stored on RCAAP IR. Other types of benefits, such as industry-academia collaboration, may happen, but the qualitative and quantitative evidence suggests that these effects are rare and difficult to attribute to RCAAP alone. More credible are benefits for institutions and academia in terms of internal efficiency, but substantial disparities between them are likely.

This case study has also highlighted the challenges in conducting such analyses for open science resources (see the following section on lessons learned). While some difficulties encountered were specific to RCAAP (e.g., complex governance with multiple layers and types of stakeholders), this experience likely provides insights transferable to other open science projects.

5.2 Lessons learned

From carrying out the cost-benefit analysis of RCAAP, several key lessons emerge that can inform future applications and similar studies. These insights are summarised below:

- **Identifying and estimating the number of users of open science projects is very challenging due to both conceptual and practical considerations (e.g., data accessibility and quality).**

There are different types of users of open science projects, ranging from people accessing the open content (without any need for registration) to people contributing to the system (e.g., by making deposits to the IR). In both cases, describing and quantifying the users may be challenging.

- Typically, open science projects—such as RCAAP—do not track individual users directly. Any estimation of users must be derived from external (e.g., Google Analytics) or internal tools (e.g., statistics plug-in for DSpace). However, this data can be imperfect due to the collection method (based on IP address) but also to the fragmentation of the IR. Indeed, the existence of different repositories (especially LOCAL ones) implies that the consolidation and aggregation of all statistics can be a challenge.
- It also implies that users' profiles are typically only tangentially known, beyond basic information such as geographical origin (subject to limitations as well). Collecting this granular information with surveys (e.g., occupation, age...) is a way forward, but it can be biased by differential participation.
- **Attributing costs for open science projects is not trivial, especially when multiple layers of institutions and users are involved, as is the case for RCAAP:**
 - Institutions do not always keep ad-hoc budgetary records of the resources they spend to run their open resources. While the data was well consolidated at the RCAAP central level, specific institutions do not keep a dedicated budget to track their IR expenses. Typically, this budget is diluted in the broader library or university budget. It implies a granular work of reconstruction of the costs, which can be done thanks to insights from in-depth interviews, external data and the scientific literature.
 - Time spent by users is a flexible approach to approximate the costs they face when carrying out activities related to open resources. However, collecting credible information regarding this time spent can be challenging. In particular, there is a strong anchoring effect due to the provided options in closed questions of a survey. Backing the estimates with multiple sources of evidence (e.g., interviews, focus group) is paramount to ensure quality.
- **Defining the counterfactual for open science projects is not straightforward - especially in the broader context of the development of initiatives such as IR. This has implications for the ability to measure costs and benefits.**

To estimate the net value provided by open science projects, it is crucial to choose an appropriate counterfactual, such as what the alternative would have been without the project. This is a core principle of CBA, as it allows an incremental comparison.

However, defining the counterfactual for RCAAP was very challenging. Indeed, several resources could have been open even without RCAAP, and alternatives were numerous. Similarly, IR could have been developed even without RCAAP, though at higher costs (and perhaps at a different pace). In addition, the case study compared two scenarios of open repositories: one with integration/pooling of resources (RCAAP) and the other without (institutions managing their IR on their own). Indeed, it was not meaningful in this case to have a comparison against a fully closed alternative, which may be relevant for other types of open science resources.

Overall, it was difficult for respondents (survey, interviews...) to imagine the counterfactual, leading to issues (e.g., in identifying access cost savings).

This issue was resolved by setting the counterfactual as the development of IR in Portugal without RCAAP, which excludes the pooling benefits provided by centralisation. However, this necessitates some assumptions which can be challenged under different grounds (e.g., the ability of small institutions to run IR without support).

- **Identifying the long-term or indirect effects of open science projects is challenging, and qualitative methods may be more flexible in some cases.**

Considering the long-term or indirect effects of RCAAP was complexified by the uncertainties around the counterfactual and the limitations of methods to reach that end. Quantitative methods (such as analysis of industry-academia collaborations using publication data) can be used but pose methodological challenges (e.g., causality). Preliminary evidence suggests minor economic effects. Qualitative methods (notably interviews and survey open-ended questions) proved more valuable in collecting insights on potential indirect/long-term effects but with limitations regarding generalizability.

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Annexes

Annex 1: Methodological toolkit

The assessment presented in this deliverable draws upon a comprehensive and multi-dimensional methodological approach that integrates both primary and secondary data sources, as well as qualitative and quantitative analytical techniques. The objective was to produce a robust, evidence-based evaluation of RCAAP's value and impact. The methodological toolkit comprises a set of interconnected components, each offering distinct but complementary insights.

Desk research provided the foundation for designing the CBA, including methodological insights from previous studies, functioning of Institutional Repositories, specificities of RCAAP (e.g., impact pathways, governance and user groups...).

Quantitative data was used to describe and forecast the users of RCAAP, as well as the budgetary aspects.

The user survey offered detailed information on usage patterns, perceived value, user benefits that are not otherwise quantifiable, and scenarios without RCAAP. Time monetisation enabled the translation of these elements into costs and benefits integrable to the CBA.

Semi-structured interviews and focus groups added qualitative depth and served to refine our understanding of the system, collect additional data (notably on costs at the institutional level) and to validate the findings.

Other work packages of PathOS (notably Work Package 3) provided additional data to describe the impacts not directly captured by the CBA.

The sections that follow present each methodological component in more detail.

A.1.1 DESK RESEARCH

Desk research was the first step of the assessment and was conducted by using academic papers, policy reports, and other documents from the grey literature. It pursued several objectives and was organised into three major strands:

- **RCAAP project:** Materials (e.g., project documents, guidelines...) related to the history, gradual development, uses, and performance of the RCAAP project and its individual components (see, for instance, Moreira et al., 2017; Carvalho et al., 2018). The scientific literature focusing on RCAAP and/or its usage was also explored, though it remained limited at the time of the writing.
- **Institutional Repositories and related issues** (e.g., Current Research Information System – CRIS): Documents related to the experience of other IR and

associated information systems, providing insights on typical organisation, procedures, policies, users' experience and costs and benefits (e.g., Angelo, 2014; Bryant et al., 2018; Esse and Haliso, 2024; Knowledge E, 2020; Lipinski, 2011; Rodrigues et al., 2024; Shearer et al., 2023). It allows contextualisation of the Portuguese case, the definition of the likely impact pathways, and data collection for potential extrapolations.

- **Methodological insights:** Potential methodological feedback related to the assessment of IR and similar initiatives were also collected. It includes CBA and other assessment methodologies (e.g., Bluh, 2009; Burns, Lana, and Budd, 2013; White and Crawford, 1998; Swan, Picarra, and Rodrigues, 2016).

A.1.2 ANALYSIS OF QUANTITATIVE DATA

In the context of the RCAAP case study, quantitative data was retrieved primarily from the RCAAP central level. This data fed the analysis for the historical period as well as for the two years of the forecast (2025 and 2026). It contributed to two aspects:

- **Budgetary data:** Data from the RCAAP central level allowed a mapping of expenditure borne by the overall functioning of the system, excluding its component institutions. It was provided by FCCN/FCT and discussed on several iterations to interpret it and complete missing information (e.g., first years prior to the launch, additional expenditure not covered in the initial budget, etc.). Budgetary data at the institutional level was mostly derived from interviews (see below) and from the secondary literature.
- **Use data:** As an open resource, RCAAP does not require registration for users searching and downloading content. As a result, use data can be monitored indirectly, through web traffic and downloads data. This information was retrieved from RCAAP at the central level (Google Analytics for views/traffic, internal statistical module for downloads). This data has some limitations (e.g. Ross et al., 2024; Beagrie and Houghton, 2021, 2016; Fomitchev, 2010), but some corrections were already applied (e.g., to remove duplicates) in the received data, and it was used directly as inputs for the CBA. Missing data (e.g., for some years) was extrapolated using proxy information (e.g., use of data on downloads to reconstruct estimates for the number of users in some years, etc.).

A.1.3 USER SURVEY

This tool was used to collect descriptive information on the users of RCAAP (e.g., age, professional background, uses of RCAAP, etc.) and primary data on the perceived value of the project.

The questionnaire was structured in three sections: Section A – General Information: it investigated respondents' profile (e.g. country of work, professional status, research fields/job details, etc); Section B – Experience with RCAAP: it investigated on the usage of the resources (e.g. frequency, combination with other sources, time used, overall satisfaction etc); Section C –

Assessment of the value of RCAAP: it included questions investigating time savings, potential alternatives if RCAAP did not exist.

The questionnaire was developed in subsequent rounds of consultation between the team, the University of Minho, and six scoping interviews with different users of the RCAAP Portal and repositories. The survey was implemented using the EUSurvey tool of the European Commission in compliance with the data privacy regulations. It was disseminated with the support of the University of Minho and FCCN through different channels, including the RCAAP portal, individual repositories managed centrally by the University of Minho / FCCN, social media, and newsletters/ mailing lists.

Overall, 213³⁴ responses were collected using EUSurvey between 12 June and 16 September 2024.

Since the characteristics of the user base population are entirely unknown—apart from the global geographical distribution of users inferred from web traffic data—it was decided not to adopt a probability sampling approach. Instead, a thorough ex-post analysis was carried out, comparing the distribution of respondents by country with that of web traffic data. Users from Portugal were somewhat overrepresented in the survey results, but it aligned well with the fact that the survey also targeted researchers/librarians feeding the system, not only users searching and downloading content. The survey sample was thus used comprehensively to feed the CBA (notably on time spent for different tasks).

Nonetheless, certain limitations of the approach should be acknowledged. In particular, the absence of a defined sampling frame and the reliance on voluntary participation introduce potential self-selection bias, as those more actively engaged with the resource may have been more inclined to respond.

A.1.5 INTERVIEWS

A total of 13 interviews were conducted as of October 2024 (see the complete list in Annex 1). They aimed to understand the patterns of uses of RCAAP (Portal and IR) for different classes of users, including researchers and administrative staff from the network of institutions operating the repositories. It allowed in-depth discussions on the value and limits of RCAAP from different perspectives. A first round of interviews was carried out in parallel to the development of the questionnaire for the online survey. A total of six interviews were performed that way, collecting valuable information on RCAAP while testing the clarity of the questionnaire. A second round of interviews was conducted at a later stage with repository managers of a sample of institutions (covering the different models of repositories). These interviews focused more on the internal benefits and costs of RCAAP participation for the institutions. A total of 7 interviews

³⁴ Out of 213 responses, 15 never used RCAAP, 3 were former users and 5 had missing information.

of this type were already implemented during the project, and additional ones are under consideration to complete the sample.

A.1.6 FOCUS GROUP

A total of 8 participants were involved in a virtual focus group on 03/12/2024. This focus group was organised in the framework of WP3 and contained a section dedicated to the CBA. During this exchange, information was provided regarding key aspects of the CBA, and feedback from diverse stakeholders was retrieved in order to consolidate the model and the final draft of the case study. It included topics such as the type and depth of benefits, as well as the counterfactual scenario.

A.1.7 ADDITIONAL DATA FROM WORK PACKAGE 3

Additional data on the potential impacts of RCAAP beyond the scope of the CBA was provided by the University of Minho. This data was obtained and consolidated in the framework of Work Package 3 of the PathOS project. It mainly covers insights on RCAAP-related scientific publications (e.g., number of documents, received citations) with a particular focus on industry-academia collaborations.

Annex 2: Interviews carried out

The following Table reports the interviewees' round, date, and affiliation for each interview.

INTERVIEW ROUND	ORGANISATION	DATE
Pilot interviews (including testing of the survey)	University of Algarve	03/06/2024
	University of Minho	03/06/2024
	University of Beira Interior	04/06/2024
	University of Aveiro	04/06/2024
	University of Lisbon	04/06/2024
	CRIA	07/06/2024
Additional interviews with repository managers	NOVA University Lisbon	27/08/2024
	Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal	28/08/2024
	ISCTE – University Institute of Lisbon	29/08/2024
	University of Minho	30/08/2024
	University of Porto	08/10/2024
	University of Coimbra	09/10/2024
	ESEL - Higher School of Nursing of Lisbon	18/10/2024 (written interview)

Annex 3: Focus Group's Composition

The following Table reports the participants in the focus group co-organised with WP3.

FOCUS GROUP	ORGANISATION	DATE
Common focus group with WP3	FCT-FCCN (PTCRIS)	03/12/2024
	FCT-FCCN (RCAAP)	
	University Institute of Lisbon	
	University of Minho	
	OpenAIRE	
	Bologna University / Open Citations	
	Lisbon Nova University	